

D7.3 The distributional effects of European climate policies in the Global South

A model-assessment for Egypt

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Abstract

This paper assesses the macro- and microeconomic impacts of the European Union's Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) on Egypt, a lower middle-income country with export exposure to the EU in carbon-intensive sectors: iron and steel, aluminium, fertiliser and cement. Employing a combined macro–micro simulation approach, the analysis finds that the overall macroeconomic effects are relatively limited. This is primarily due to the modest share of CBAM-covered goods in Egypt's total exports and the country's capacity for trade diversion. However, the microsimulation results indicate regressive distributional consequences, with the most adverse effects borne by poor, rural, and unskilled households. Moreover, the gender dimension reveals that men are more affected than women, largely due to the higher concentration of male employment in the impacted industries. These findings suggest that CBAM may exacerbate poverty and inequality in vulnerable economies. The study underscores the necessity for targeted mitigation policies and demonstrates the value of integrating a computable general equilibrium (CGE) model with a behavioural microsimulation framework to capture both aggregate and distributional effects effectively.

1. Introduction

The European Union's Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) is a central element of the broader "Fit-for-55" climate strategy and the EU Green Deal. It reinforces the EU's objective of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 55% from 1990 levels by 2030 (Amendola, 2025; Guepi et al., 2023). CBAM aims to level the playing field between EU-produced and imported goods by introducing carbon tariffs for imports to the EU, thus discouraging carbon leakage¹ and promoting fair competition between domestic and international producers (Fontagne and Schubert, 2023; Beaufils et al., 2023). The mechanism primarily targets carbon-intensive imports such as cement, iron and steel, aluminium, fertilisers, electricity, and hydrogen (EU, 2023; Ghoneim, 2024). The extent of its financial and trade impacts on the exporters will depend on the export structure, development status, and EU dependency of trading partners (Ghoneim, 2024)².

CBAM is primarily designed to curb carbon leakage by imposing tariffs on imports from countries with less stringent climate policies, thereby ensuring that the EU's climate objectives are not compromised by the relocation of production to these regions (Beaufils et al., 2023; Ghoneim, 2024). Although this strategy supports the EU's environmental ambitions, it poses economic challenges for developing and least developed countries, particularly those whose economies depend on carbon-intensive exports to the EU (Guepie et al., 2023). For these countries, CBAM introduces new trade barriers that make accessing the European market more difficult in the absence of comparable climate regulations. Low- and middle-income countries, particularly in Africa, are expected to be disproportionately impacted due to their dependence on the EU market and the high carbon intensity of their exports (Guepie et al., 2023).

Welfare losses associated with CBAM are particularly pronounced in LDCs with emissions-intensive industries (Perdana and Vielle, 2022). In LDCs, the negative economic impacts can transmit to the vulnerable population and increase in poverty and inequality. Worsening the situation of poverty is an undesired effect. It is a call for climate justice as countries in the Global South, such as Egypt, bear a double burden of the European's mitigation policies. First, these countries are disproportionately vulnerable to the adverse effects of climate change, despite having contributed minimally to global carbon emissions. The primary responsibility for historical and current emissions lies with industrialised nations, including those in Europe, yet the resulting climate impacts are most acutely felt in more vulnerable Southern economies. Second, the European Union's CBAM, while designed to reduce global carbon leakage, may inadvertently exacerbate economic vulnerability, poverty, and inequality in these countries by adversely affecting carbon-intensive exports. A comprehensive theoretical and empirical assessment is therefore essential to evaluate the net effect of CBAM—balancing its intended positive environmental incentives against its potential to disrupt trade, production, and livelihoods in the Global South.

In this paper we provide empirical evidence on the impacts of the CBAM on Egypt, a Global South country characterised by carbon-intensive production and strong trade linkages with the European Union. We conduct a comprehensive analysis at both the macroeconomic and microeconomic

¹ Carbon leakage can appear if climate policies in one region drive companies to relocate carbon-intensive production to another region with laxer environmental rules. As a result carbon intensive production reduces in the region with climate policies but takes place in another region where it can even increase more the CO₂ emissions. (European Union, 2025).

² For more detailed information on CBAM see Cammeo et al. (2024, 2025).

levels. At the macro level, we employ a computable general equilibrium (CGE) model to estimate the economy-wide effects and determine whether CBAM poses a significant negative impact on Egypt’s overall economic performance. To capture the distributional consequences, the CGE model is linked with a behavioural model. This integrated approach allows us to assess the micro-level effects of CBAM, particularly its implications for poverty and inequality across different socioeconomic and demographic groups.

Egypt’s industrial sector plays a significant role in the economy, accounting for roughly one-third of GDP. The labour market is highly segregated by gender. Women work mainly in services (particularly in the public administration, education and health system) and as informal and often unpaid family workers. Men work in the primary and secondary sectors, including the CBAM industries. The CBAM industries are the highest-emitting and were responsible for around 9% of the country’s total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in 2015. Egypt’s high carbon intensity and relative high share of exports are reflected in the World Bank’s CBAM exposure index. Egypt’s index is the highest in the MENA region and indicates an increased risk of reduced export competitiveness compared to EU standards (Kamal and Ramzy, 2024).

While the CBAM exposure index indicates Egypt’s relative high exposure to CBAM, deriving the impacts based on the trade volume alone is less clear. Over the past two decades, exports from Egypt to Europe have grown substantially. Currently, the CBAM industries represent almost 20% of Egypt’s exports to the EU, with some industries facing significant exposure (Kamal and Ramzy, 2024). In 2022, CBAM-related exports, accounted for around 10% of Egypt’s total global exports (Ghoneim, 2024). These shares, indicate relative high shares of CBAM exports for Egypt, however, the volumes include refinery commodities, which are not defined as CBAM relevant for the implementation. Figure 1 illustrates Egypt’s exports of CBAM commodities to Europe as share of the total exports, only for the CBAM related commodities, excluding refinery products. While exports of cement to Europe are marginal, iron and steel, aluminium, and fertilisers comprising the largest shares, (Jacob, 2024). These sectors are likely to suffer the most from competitiveness losses. Despite a clear increasing trend, CBAM-related exports accounted for less than 5% of Egypt’s total exports in 2023. This suggests that, excluding refinery products, the economic impact of CBAM could be modest.

Figure 1: Exports of CBAM commodities to EU27 and total exports.

Source: authors' presentation based on data from ESCWA (2023)

Egypt is classified as a lower middle-income country. In 2019, 29.7% of its population lived in poverty. While poverty had been declining between 2017 and 2019, a series of global shocks—including the COVID-19 pandemic, the Russia-Ukraine war, U.S. trade-related inflation, and the Israeli-Hamas conflict—have reversed this trend, particularly affecting Egypt's vital tourism sector (World Bank, 2023a). Poverty in Egypt is multifaceted and apply to multiple dimensions: employment, housing, education, health, social protection, and food security. In 2022, over 20% of Egyptians were considered multidimensionally poor. Food insecurity is particularly severe, with 48.8% of the population affected. As one of the world's most food-import-dependent nations—importing around 40% of its food by value—Egypt is especially vulnerable to global price shocks, which disproportionately affect low-income households (ESCWA, 2024; Newman, 2024).

Several studies analyse the impacts of CBAM on Southern Countries. Salisu and Adediran (2025) find a real output decline of 1.48% in the Global South varying between the regions Africa, MENA, Asia Pacific (excl. China) and Americas (Salisu and Adediran 2025). Guepie et al. (2022) examined both aggregate and disaggregated impacts of CBAM on Africa, finding GDP reductions ranging from 1.5% to 8.4%, with strongest losses for Djibouti, Liberia, and Togo. In the same study, the authors estimate export declines of 5.8% overall and substantial reductions in specific sectors—fertilisers (3.9%), electricity (9.2%), iron and steel (8.1%), aluminium (11.6%), and cement (3.1%). Perdana and Vielle (2022) report that CBAM could reduce carbon leakage from 17% to 12.6% by 2040, however for the cost of significant welfare losses in Africa and Asia. Amendola (2025) finds that CBAM sectors are more likely to face revenue losses resulting in distributional impacts. Beaufilet et al. (2023) emphasise that middle- and low-income countries heavily reliant on the EU market are particularly at risk.

For Egypt, Ghoneim (2024) anticipates significant impacts. Jacob (2024) finds that among Mediterranean countries Egypt fertiliser sector is particularly vulnerable despite a relative low export intensity. He forecasts the impact on CBAM industries causes job and wage losses. While the general economic impacts are expected to be negative, Kamal and Ramzy (2024) expect that Egyptian firms which are already engaged in emissions monitoring and cleaner production may even find opportunities to strengthen their competitiveness, compared to firms who have not yet started the transition.

While much of the papers focus on macroeconomic and trade effects (e.g., Guepie et al., 2022) or firm-level impacts (e.g., Kamal and Ramzy, 2024; Kamal et al., 2024), papers on CBAM's distributive effects remain scarce. Timilsina and Sebsibie (2024) analyse general carbon pricing policies in Egypt but not specifically for CBAM. This paper seeks to contribute filling that gap. We conduct simulations of CBAM impacts using a dynamic CGE model for macroeconomic analysis and a behavioural microsimulation model for microeconomic analysis. In this top-down modelling approach, the CGE model is employed to simulate the macroeconomic effects of the CBAM. The CGE model provides detailed information on changes in key economic indicators such as sectoral output, prices, and wages resulting from the implementation of CBAM. These results are then passed to the behavioural microsimulation model, which uses them to estimate the impacts on individual households. This integrated framework facilitates a nuanced distributive analysis, capturing how macroeconomic changes translate into effects on poverty and inequality across different population groups.

Our results indicate that the simulated implementation of the CBAM has only modest effects on Egypt's overall economy. This is largely due to the relatively small share of CBAM-covered products in Egypt's total exports. However, despite these limited macroeconomic impacts, the microsimulation analysis reveals adverse effects at the household level, particularly in terms of increased poverty and reduced food security. The findings also highlight gendered labour market

impacts: men are more negatively affected than women, as they are disproportionately employed in CBAM-related sectors such as industry, making them more vulnerable to employment and income shocks induced by the policy.

The following section (Section 2) outlines the research methodology, presenting both the macroeconomic and microeconomic models employed in the analysis. Section 3 describes the two simulated scenarios based on different carbon price assumptions. Section 4 presents and discusses the results of the simulations. Finally, Section 5 concludes by highlighting the key contributions of the study and suggesting avenues for future research.

2. Methodology

2.1 Macroeconomic model

Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models serve as analytical tools for assessing the ex-ante impacts of the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) on third-country economies, as they facilitate a coherent representation of economic flows and capture the intersectoral linkages within the economy (Böhringer et al., 2012; Perdana and Vielle, 2022). CGE models have been applied in various studies to simulate CBAM scenarios, e.g., Guepie et al. (2023), Perdana and Vielle (2022), and UNCTAD (2021). In this paper, we use a dynamic CGE model to simulate the macroeconomic impacts of CBAM on Egypt.

2.1.1 Macroeconomic data

As data base to calibrate the CGE standard model PEP-1-t we use the Social Accounting Matrix (SAM) provided by and described in Serag et al. (2021). To obtain a CGE model customised to the specific research question, we extend this SAM by CBAM commodities and trade partners and by gendered labour markets.

2.1.1.1 Extending the SAM by CBAM commodities

First, the original SAM To account for CBAM commodities and Europe as a specific trade partner, the original SAM from Serag et al. (2021) is extended by (1) (i) disaggregating the trade partners as different agents (i.e., EU27 and the Rest of the World (ROW)), (ii) including the CBAM commodities in the SAM (i.e., petrol, fertiliser, cement, iron and steel and aluminium). As a result we obtain a SAM which differs from the original SAM according to Table 1. We validate the resulting trade shares by comparing them with another research study³.

Table 1: Comparison of the original SAM and the SAM extended by CBAM

	SAM original	SAM-CBAM
Trade partners	EGY and ROW	EGY, EU27 and ROW
CBAM commodities	Petrol, fertiliser, iron and steel	Petrol, fertiliser, iron and steel, cement, and aluminium

³ For detailed information of the technical steps of the extension and the validation see the Annex.

2.1.1.2 Expanding the SAM by gendered labour

To assess the gendered impacts of CBAM, from the original SAM we disaggregated the labour market by gender. Indeed, the labour market in Egypt is highly segmented with skilled women working mainly in administration and unskilled women working in agricultural sectors.

For differentiating the labour markets we use the microeconomic data by (ERF and CAPMAS, 2019). Table 2 presents the differences between the original SAM and the extended SAM. The original SAM provides 69 activities and 8 labour types without gender differentiation. In the CBAM extended SAM we differentiate each of the labour types into male and female labour force. The microdata used for the split (i.e., the Egypt Labour Market Panel Survey, ELMPS (2018) (ERF and CAPMAS, 2019) provide only 10 economic sectors (i.e., activities). Therefore, we aggregate the number of sectors in the extended SAM. With 10 sectors the CGE model is consistent with the microsimulation model, using the same micro data set. Being in line with the micro data for the proportions of men and women in each of the 10 sectors keep us from making assumptions on the other sectors we would have kept. As the CGE model is providing results at the sectoral level to the micro model, it is important to be as close as possible in terms of sectors.

Distributive aspects are typically understood as variations in poverty or income distribution across households or individuals belonging to different population groups. In this study, the original SAM distinguishes household groups by income quintiles in both rural and urban areas. Economic shocks—such as the introduction of CBAM as a tariff-like measure—transmit to individuals primarily through commodity markets, via changes in prices, and through the labour market, via changes in employment and wages. The latter directly affects household income and consumption capacity. The transmission of such shocks through the labour market may differ by gender, particularly in contexts where the labour market is gender-segregated, as is the case in Egypt. This study incorporates a gender-disaggregated labour market dimension, enabling a more nuanced analysis of the socio-economic impacts. The microsimulation model facilitates a closer examination of gender-specific effects that would be obscured in analyses conducted at more aggregated levels.

Table 2: Comparison of the original SAM and the SAM extended by gendered labour market

	SAM original	SAM-CBAM
Sectors / activities	69	10
Labour types	8 (4 educational levels, 2 regional levels)	16 (4 educational levels, 2 regional levels, 2 gender)

2.1.1.3 CO2 emission data

To quantify the CO2 emissions resulting from economic activities we apply the CO2 emission quantities provided by the GTAP11 database (Aguiar et al., 2023). The CO2 emission quantities for production, imports and consumption allow to compute CO2 emissions in the base situation and in the scenarios and derive the change in emission quantities resulting from the implementation of CBAM.

2.1.2 The Social Accounting Matrix (SAM)

The SAM serves as a data base to which the CGE model is calibrated. Thus, describing the structure of the SAM supports the understanding of the results. The information gained from the analysis of the structure can help to explain the reaction of the CGE model. . For a detailed description of the SAM, see the Annex.

2.1.2.1 Contribution of sector value-added

Table 3 presents the contribution of the value added of each sector to the total value added generated in the economy in 2019 (base year of our SAM). The main contributors to the value-added (and thus to the national GDP) are with 22%, the service sectors (e.g., hotels and restaurants, trade, transport), followed by the manufacturing sector with 15%. The manufacturing sector includes the production of the CBAM products petrol, fertiliser, cement, iron and steel and aluminium. Table 3 also provides information on how exposed to the external market the different sectors are.

These share measure, the sector's export performance, and dependence of this sector on fluctuations in demand or world prices. Most of the Egyptian production is sold on the domestic market.

In Table 4, the first column presents the ratio of local sales compared to total production. For most of the commodities the ratio is close to one, meaning that most of the commodities are sold on the local market, excluding petroleum products, textiles and tourism services (i.e., hotels and restaurant). For the CBAM commodities cement, fertiliser, iron and steel and aluminium, the ratio are relatively high indicating that most of the production is sold domestically too. Thus, the changes CBAM tariffs on exports caused on the economy might be limited. The main exported products are tourism-related products (hotels, restaurants), transportation and storage, and to a lesser extent mining products (crude oil, natural gas and other mining products).

A similar calculation can be applied to imports. Thus, the import penetration rate (second column in Table 4), i.e. the share of imports in the total resources of the product on the domestic market, is high for agricultural commodities, especially oilseed (coils), or wheat (cwhea) for which imports represent more than 40% of what is on the market. This import dependency for agricultural commodity indicates the vulnerability of Egypt to increases in world food prices. The import penetration is also high for vehicle equipment (cvehi, 72%) or other manufacturing (coman, 85%). In terms of the share of sectoral imports in total imports, they mainly import industrial commodities such as vehicle equipment (8% of total imports, in the third column.), i.e. the share of imports in the total resources of the product on the domestic market, is high for agricultural commodities, especially oilseed (coils), or wheat (cwhea) for which imports represent more than 40% of what is on the market. This import dependency for agricultural commodity indicates the vulnerability of Egypt to increases in world food prices. The import penetration is also high for vehicle equipment

(cvehi, 72%) or other manufacturing (coman, 85%). In terms of the share of sectoral imports in total imports, they mainly import industrial commodities such as vehicle equipment (8% of total imports, in the third column).

Table 3: Contribution of each sector to the total value added and production for domestic supply and exports

	Contribution to total value added	Domestic supply	Export
	% of total value added	% share domestic sales out of total production	% share exports out of total production
aagforfish	15.8	95.1	4.9
amanuf	15.4	87.5	12.5
aotherind	10.1	89.7	10.3
acons	5.3	98.3	1.7
atrad	11.4	100.0	0.0
atran	8.2	69.5	30.5
apadm	4.5	93.6	6.4
aeduc	5.5	100.0	0.0
aheal	2.2	100.0	0.0
aserv	21.5	85.5	14.5

Note: agrforfis = agriculture & forestry & fishery, amanuf = manufacturing, otherindu = other industries, acons = construction, atrad = trade, atran = transport, apadm = public services, aeduc = education, aheal = health services, aserv = other services.

Table 4: Indicators describing the trade relations

	Imports			Exports		
	Locally sold/ total produced	% import penetration	% share of imports	to Non-EU in % of total exports	to EU in % of total exports	% share of total exports
cmaiz	97.9	28.3	2.8	0.2		0.2
cwhea	100.0	41.3	1.1			
coils	97.1	56.4	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.1
cfrocrp	86.9	9.5	1.8	2.5	0.7	3.2
coliv	93.7	0.3	0.0	1.2	0.1	1.3
ccoil	89.8	10.8	2.6	1.5	1.6	3.1
cngas	87.5			1.8	0.5	2.3
comin	67.2	26.5	2.1	3.2	0.4	3.6
cfveg	85.1	18.2	1.4	1.3	0.1	1.4
cfood	94.4	10.1	2.0	1.1	0.2	1.3
ctext	36.8			1.8	0.8	2.7
cclth	72.2	47.6	3.8	1.5	0.5	2.0
cpetr	36.8	31.8	1.6	5,3	2,1	7,4
cfert	95.9	14.9	7.0	1,4	0,7	2,1
cnmet	72.7	5.8	0.2	1,2	0,3	1,6
cement	97.6	3.7	0.4	0,4	0,0	0,4
cmetl	89.6	3.4	0.1	0,4	0,0	0,4
ciron	69.5	40.0	1.4	1,0	0,2	1,1
calumin	89.3	43.5	5.1	0,7	0,4	1,0
cmach	98.7	5.8	0.5	0.1	0.0	0.1
cequi	72.8	45.1	5.6	2.5	0.7	3.2
cvehi	97.0	71.7	7.9	0.1	0.0	0.1
coman	63.0	85.1	4.5	0.5	0.1	0.6
chotrest	19.3			16.9	6.9	23.7
cbsrv	85.9	24.4	4.6	1.7	1.3	3.0
cpadm	89.9			1.9	0.2	2.1
chem	89.6			4.8	1.9	6.8
ctrans	65.7	20.7	7.6	12.5	6.8	19.3

Note: cmaiz = maize commodity, crice = rice, cwhea = cwhea, croot = root crops, cfrocrp = fruits and other crops, ccatt= cattle, coliv= other livestock, cfore = forestry, cfish= fishery, cngas = natural gas, cmeat = meat, cdair = dairy products, cfveg = vegetable and vegetable oils, cgml = milling products, csref = sugar refinery, cfood = food processing, cbeve = beverages, ctext = textiles, cclth = clothes and shoes, cleat = leather articles, cpapr = paper, cpetr = petroleum; cnmet = non-metal minerals, cement = cement, cmetl = metals, ciron = iron and steel products, calumin = aluminium products, cmach = machines, cequi = machinery and equipments, cvehi = vehicles, coman = other manufacturing products, celec = electricity, cwatr = water distribution services, ccons = construction, chotrest = hotel and restaurant,

2.1.3 The CGE model

To evaluate the impacts of the implementation of the CBAM on the Egyptian economy, we develop a dynamic CGE model based on the PEP-1-t model by (Decaluwé et al., 2013). However, to represent the specificities of the country and the research question we are interested in, we changed many hypotheses from the standard model. The model is calibrated to the SAM described in the previous section and in the Annex.

2.1.3.1 Activities

In consistency with the SAM, we represent 10 economic sectors by 10 activities, which production is defined by a multi-level nested structure. Figure 2 represents the production in the CGE model as a production tree scheme. At the top level, output is a Leontief type of function between value added and intermediate consumption. At the second level, value added is defined in terms of a CES function between composite labour and composite capital. At the third level, composite labour is disaggregated between rural and urban labour. At the fourth level, each type of labour is further disaggregated between skilled labour and unskilled labour. Skilled labour is further disaggregated by skill into low- and skilled labour. Low skilled workers is a CES type of function between workers illiterate and workers who have not finished the primary level of education. Each type of education category is then split into male and female. Skilled workers are split between workers who have finished the tertiary level of education and workers who have finished the secondary level of education. Here as well, each type of worker category is further split by gender.

Figure 2: Production tree with gendered labour

Note: Illiter. = unskilled, illiterate labour, Prim. = primary education, Seco. = secondary education, Terti. = tertiary education

Table 5 presents the shares of labour to the value added per sector. For agricultural sector the contribution of labour accounts around 40%. Manufacturing and other industries are with 20 to 30%

of labour contribution rather capital intensive, while public services, education and health demand for 70% to nearly 90% of labour. Figure 3 illustrates the composition of labour in each sector by the share of wage bills. In most of the sectors male labour (blue and grey) are dominating to female labour (red and yellow). Particularly in manufacturing (including the production of CBAM commodities), construction and transport. Sectors such as health and education are particularly female intensive in Egypt. Since, we represent only formally employed workers in the CGE model, it is important to also keep in mind that in Egypt most of the women are working informally and as family workers.

Table 5: Labour contribution to value added in each sector

	% of labour to value added
agrforfis	42.4
amanuf	28.6
otherindu	24.2
acons	52.3
atrad	36.2
atran	71.2
apadm	88.3
aeduc	88.2
aheal	52.9
aserv	52.5

Notes: agrforfis = agriculture & forestry & fishery, amanuf = manufacturing, otherindu = other industries, acons = construction, atrad = trade, atran = transport, apadm = public services, aeduc = education, aheal = health services, aserv = other services

Figure 3: Share of specific wage bill in the value added per sector

Note: agrforfis = agriculture & forestry & fishery, amanuf = manufacturing, otherindu = other industries, acons = construction, atrad = trade, atran = transport, apadm = public services, aeduc = education, aheal = health services, aserv = other services

2.1.3.2 Income

Figure 4 presents the shares of households' income sources. The CGE model simulates ten types of households split according to their income quintile and their location (rural or urban). Households' income is derived from male and female labour, capital and transfers from other institutions (i.e., remittances, dividends, government transfers). For all households labour is the largest source of income, while for poorest households (i.e., hhd-u1 and hhd-r1) the share of income from transfers is bigger, for the richest households (i.e., hhd-u5 and hhd-r5) the income from capital is high. All households use their income to consume, pay direct taxes, pay transfers to other institutions and save. Household behaviour on the consumption side is modelled as a Linear Expenditure System (LES).

Figure 4: Households source of income

Note: hhd- = household income decile, -r1= rural first decile, ..., r5 = rural fifth decile, -u1= urban first decile, ..., u5 = urban fifth decile, YHL = income from labour, YHK = income form capital, YHTR = income from transfers

Figure 5 presents the repartition of labour income. Rural households receive mainly labour income from male rural who have finished their secondary level (i.e., skilled labour). For the richest rural households, it is mainly male secondary and male tertiary labour income that contributes to total wage earnings. Female labour earning is relatively low for each type of rural households. This observation is not surprising since only few women work in salaried employment. For urban households, the richest households receive labour income from workers who have finished their tertiary education (i.e., skilled labour). For urban households, the contribution to total income of low skilled women labour income is marginal.

Firms⁴ derive their income from capital and from transfers from the government and the rest of the world. All firms pay dividends to other agents, direct taxes and they save. Government income is composed of transfers income, and direct and indirect taxes. The government spends most of its income on consumption (e.g., administration, education), transfers to other institutions and saves the rest.

⁴ In the CGE-model we represent firms as aggregated agent.

Figure 5: Repartition of labour income

2.1.3.3 Trade

To represent Egypt's trade relations with its trading partners, we disaggregate the single trade agent "Rest of the World" (ROW) as it is set in the PEP-1-t standard model. We identify Egypt's trade flows with Europe and with the Rest of the World excluding the Europe. Following Armington's traditional assumptions for international trade, Egyptian producers have the choice between exporting and selling their production locally. If Egyptian producer choose to export, they have the choice of exporting to Europe or to the Rest of the World excluding Europe. On the exports side, it is assumed that export demand has a finite elasticity, reflecting the competitiveness of local producers on the international markets. This implies that Egyptian producers need to be more competitive than foreign producers to increase their world market shares.

Figure 6 presents the trade flows for aggregated trade (left) and the disaggregated trade without services (right). The bars on the left-hand side in each diagram represent the quantity of exports from Egypt, the two bars on the right-hand side represent the trade partners Europe (EU27) and the Rest of the World (ROW) to which the exports are directed. The diagram on the left illustrates that the export of the tertiary sectors (services) is account equals to the aggregated trade volume from primary (agriculture) and secondary (industry) sector. Thus, exports from industry (including the production of CBAM commodities) account for only one third of the total exports. Out of the exports from industry less than one fourth is exported to Europe. The exports to the Rest of the World are significantly bigger for primary, secondary and tertiary sectors. The diagram on the right displays the disaggregated industries excluding the service sectors. The lowest export bars represent the CBAM commodities, including petrol products. Compared to the other industries only petrol represents a considerable share. The other CBAM commodities are very small and their exports to Europe appear to be even very small.

These illustrations demonstrate that compared to the total of exports of primary and secondary sectors, the share of CBAM commodities is small; if compared to the total of exports including services, the share of CBAM commodities is marginal. If refinery products (i.e., petroleum) are included within the CBAM commodities, the total of affected exports to Europe reaches a larger, but

still relatively small share of total exports. This means, if the tariff is not extremely (unrealistically) high, the CGE model might not react with significant changes, since the share of the affected commodities are small compared to what is not impacted by the tariff. Furthermore, the graphs show, that Egypt exports mostly to the Rest of the World. Within the model and in the real world, the redirection of exports that are not going anymore to Europe if the CBAM tariff is implemented can be absorbed by the Rest of the World.

Figure 6: Trade flows from Egypt to EU27 and the rest of the world (ROW)

Source: SAM data. Note: Left diagram: aggregated trade flows from Egypt's (left bars) to ROW and EU27 (right bars). Right diagram: disaggregated trade (flows excl. services) from Egypt (left bars) to ROW and EU (right bars)

2.1.3.4 Closure rules

To analyse the impact of the implementation of the CBAM on the Egyptian economy, we simulate a period of 10 years, reaching from the base year 2019 to 2029. The equilibrium in each market is achieved through changes in relative prices and quantities supplied and demanded. The nominal exchange rate is fixed as the numeraire of the model. We assume that Egypt is a small country, which does not influence world prices. Thus, the world prices are fixed. The current account balance is assumed to be exogenously fixed. This assumption implies that Egypt cannot borrow from the Rest of the World, and that any reduction in imports necessarily leads to a reduction in exports. Defining an endogenous current account balance would allow the country to have its policy financed by the rest of the world without ever having to repay it. This assumption seems to be unrealistic for our scenario analysis. Government's savings is endogenous while government spending in goods and services is fixed. Thus, a decrease in government's income leads to a decrease in its savings, which will have an impact on the total investment budget.

Given the labour market situation in Egypt, we replace the full employment assumption in PEP-1-t model by modelling unemployment. We follow the Blanchflower and Oswald (1995) specification, which represent the empirical relation between unemployment rate and wage rates. Blanchflower and Oswald (1995) found that a 10% increase in the unemployment rate leads to a 1% decrease in wages. Labour is mobile across sectors whereas capital is sector specific. The stock of labour rises at the population growth rate each year while the stock of capital of each sector depends on the new investments made in the sector. The allocation of new investment follows the accumulation equation of Jung and Thorbecke (2003). In the absence of shocks, the economy grows naturally at the population growth rate as the Business as Usual (BAU) scenario. The effects resulting from the scenario simulations are compared to the corresponding year of the BAU.

2.2 Microeconomic model

Egypt's labour market is characterised by pronounced gender disparities. Female labour force participation remains low, largely due to entrenched cultural norms that emphasize women's domestic roles. Gender wage gaps are substantial—especially in the private sector—and occupational segregation limits women's access to higher-paying and secure employment. These constraints are reinforced by prevailing societal expectations that uphold the male breadwinner model, further restricting women's access to quality jobs (Miyata and Yamada, 2016; Biltagy, 2019; Omran and Bilan, 2022).

2.2.1 Microeconomic data

Our microsimulation intends to model such labour market by drawing on two main data sources: the 2018 Labour Force Survey (LFS) (OAMDI, 2021), and the 2018 Household Survey (OAMDI, 2023). The LFS provides detailed individual-level information on employment outcomes, while the Household Survey offers complementary data on household welfare, including disaggregated food expenditure (food security proxy) and non-labour income sources such as self-employment, rental income, property returns, and transfers.

Since the household and labour force surveys do not follow the same households, we chose the LFS as our primary dataset, and supplemented it with some variables from the Household Survey. To do this, we implement a matching algorithm⁵ that identifies comparable households across the two datasets. To assess the reliability of this procedure, poverty and inequality indicators were calculated using the matched dataset and compared with official statistics. At the national poverty line of 736 Egyptian pounds per person per month, the matched data yielded a poverty rate of 30%, closely aligning with the official estimate of 32.5%. The Gini coefficient from the matched dataset was 0.307, compared to the official figure of 0.315—indicating that the matching preserved key distributional characteristics.

2.2.2 The Microsimulation model

Price channel

The macroeconomic model generates highly disaggregated price shocks across approximately 70 goods and services, which must be mapped to household-level expenditure data. Each household displays a unique consumption pattern across these categories; thus, the impact of price changes varies depending on the composition of its expenditure basket⁶. The household specific consumer price index (CPI) following the price shock is calculated using the Laspeyres definition, which considers household-level budget shares. Denoted the pre-shock and post-shocks as P_j^0 (before) and

⁵ We employ a nearest neighborhood hot deck approach available in R (library StatMatch). Although the matching was performed at the household level, we employed a variety of demographic indicators including indicators of the distribution of individual characteristics within the household

⁶ Because of their highly regulated price system, price variation is limited, which discourages the estimation of expenditure lineal system that endogenize the expenditure shares as a function of commodity prices.

P_j^1 respectively and the share of item j in household i 's budget as s_{ji} , the CPI for household i is defined as:

$$CPI_i = \prod_j \left(\frac{P_j^1}{P_j^0} \right)^{s_{ji}}$$

The labour market channel

The microsimulation model reflects the labour mobility assumptions embedded in the CGE framework. Wage workers are assumed to be mobile across economic sectors and only marginally into unemployment, but not across skill levels or geographic locations. Specifically, labour is segmented by urban/rural location and four education tiers (illiterate, primary, secondary, tertiary) forming distinct groups within which mobility is allowed.

Sectoral transitions are modelled based on a set of demographic and human capital characteristics that influence the likelihood of moving between sectors or exiting employment. These constraints are particularly binding for women, who tend to be concentrated in sectors such as agriculture, education, and public administration. As widely documented in the literature, cultural norms, caregiving responsibilities, and household dynamics continue to shape both labour supply and demand for women in Egypt (Krafft and Assaad, 2022; Miyata and Yamada, 2016; Biltagy, 2019; Omran and Bilan, 2022). Accordingly, the model includes regressors that inform sectoral mobility for both men and women within their respective skill-location groups. More specifically, labour income is estimated using a Heckman selection model to address potential participation bias. For an individual i in sector j , the wage is modelled as:

$$\ln w_{ij} = x_i' \beta_j^g + u_{ij}$$

Where x_i' includes variables such as age, age squared, years of education, urban/rural residence, and the household head's education level. Gender-specific coefficients β_j^g are estimated separately for each group. Selection into sectoral employment is modelled through a probit equation:

$$\Pr[J = j]_i = \Phi(x_i' \gamma_j^g + z_i' \theta_j^g)$$

with exclusion restrictions z_i' including variables like number of children, number of elderly household members, and the share of female members—proxies for household caregiving responsibilities that may affect labour participation, particularly for women.

Following sector-specific labour demand shocks from the CGE model, the microsimulation determines which individuals are most likely to switch jobs between sectors based on predicted participation probabilities, $\Pr[J = j]_i$. Counterfactual labour income is simulated using the estimated wage equations, assuming normally distributed errors u_{ij} , as in Bourguignon and Spadaro (2006).

The microsimulation also incorporates other (less important) sources of income from the CGE model by applying a flat average rate —e.g., the same relative increase within each subcategory of

gender region and income quintile. The final household simulated income that results from the aggregation of different sources of income (after the shock), is then deflated by the household-specific post-shock CPI_i . This simulated real income is denoted Y_{S_i} .

Our welfare analysis requires simulating household consumption after a shock (C_{S_i}), which is obtained by assuming a household-specific average propensity to consume c_i defined from the original data as the household consumption to income ratio, i.e. $c_i = C_i/Y_i$. The simulated consumption is then calculated from the simulated income as $C_{S_i} = c_i Y_{S_i}$.

Food security

Our food security indicator, denoted f_h , is proxied by the per-capita expenditure on food items at the household level. The food expenditure poverty line used in the calculation of the FGT indices was computed as the average value of food expenditure of households whose total expenditures lay within a $\pm 1\%$ bandwidth around the absolute poverty line. We model food expenditure as a function of the logarithm of household per capita total real income (y_h), using as controls (x'_h) the marital status, household size, the share of females of the household, the number of children below the age of 14 years, and the number of people older than 65 years.

$$\ln f_h = x'_h \beta + \theta \ln y_h + \epsilon_h$$

The simulated food security, \hat{f}_h is obtained by replacing the simulated real income after a shock \hat{y}_h and its corresponding residual $\hat{\epsilon}_h$ into the estimated equation.

3. Scenarios

To evaluate the potential impacts of CBAM on Egypt, we simulate two scenarios. In the first scenario (*Sim 1*), we simulate the CBAM applied to the four products fertilisers, aluminium, iron and cement in 2026 and the introduction of oil products in 2028. Oriented to Xiaobei et al (2022), we assume a conservative EU carbon price of 75 USD per ton of CO₂. To compute the tariff equivalent, we use the sectoral level carbon emission data derived from the GTAP database. In the second scenario (*Sim 2*), we increase the EU carbon price to 100 USD per ton of CO₂. The higher carbon price increases the customs duties on Egyptian exports to Europe. As a comparison in a CGE model study by Guepie et al., (2022). The authors simulate scenarios of carbon prices of 48 and 96 USD per ton of CO₂⁷. Thus, the prices of 75 and 100 USD per ton of CO₂ are in the magnitude of prices by other authors.

⁷ Guepie et al. (2022) indicate the carbon prices as 40 and 87 EUR per ton CO₂. We use the currency conversions of 1 EUR = 1.1992 USD to convert the price of 40 EUR/t and 1 EUR = 1.1061 USD to convert the price of 87 EUR/t, representing the periods from February to March 2021 and the year 2022.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 CGE model results

4.1.1 Macroeconomic impacts

The introduction of CBAM tariffs on Egyptian exports of cement, aluminium, fertilisers, and steel to Europe makes these products for Egypt less competitive and therefore reducing their trade flows. For these specific products, export flows decrease, which reduces the production of these products. Consequently, employment in these sectors decreases; and the sectors reduce their intermediate consumption of other commodities, affecting other sectors of the economy. Overall, the impact on GDP is slightly negative (Table 6) and prices (CPI) are decreasing slightly (-0.017% in 2026). With the introduction of oil as a product taxed by the CBAM starting in 2028, the impacts are a little stronger but remain modest on the Egyptian economy with real GDP decreasing by 0.013% in 2028 in *Sim 1* and 0.017% in *Sim 2* assuming a higher carbon price. The relative small changes in the economy result in small decreasing in CO2 emissions ranging from 0.02% to 0.06%.

Table 6: Impact on macroeconomic variables (in % to the BAU)

	Sim 1		Sim 2	
	2026	2028	2026	2028
Real GDP	-0.004	-0.013	-0.005	-0.017
Total Investment	-0.029	-0.086	-0.037	-0.114
Total labour demand	-0.008	-0.026	-0.011	-0.034
Total exports	-0.013	-0.041	-0.017	-0.054
CPI	-0.017	-0.050	-0.022	-0.065
Total CO2 emissions	-0.016	-0.049	-0.021	-0.064

After the implementation of the CBAM tariff in 2026, exports to Europe of the four targeted products decrease significantly (-2.4% for fertilisers, -4.7% for iron and steel, -1.8% for cement, -1.1% for aluminium, see Table 7). For the other commodities, the changes are modest, they are slightly increasing given that the Egyptian commodities are relatively cheaper given the drop in prices. Egypt redirects some of the CBAM commodities originally exported to Europe to the Rest of the World. The relative changes of exports to the Rest of the World are small.

Table 7: Impacts on exports to the EU27 and to the ROW (in % to the BAU)

	EU27				ROW			
	Sim 1		Sim 2		Sim 1		Sim 2	
	2026	2028	2026	2028	2026	2028	2026	2028
cmaiz	0.010	0.029	0.013	0.038	0.010	0.029	0.013	0.038
croot	0.010	0.029	0.013	0.038	0.010	0.029	0.013	0.038
cfrocrp	0.010	0.029	0.013	0.038	0.010	0.029	0.013	0.038
coliv	0.010	0.029	0.013	0.038	0.010	0.029	0.013	0.038
cfore	0.010	0.030	0.013	0.039	0.010	0.030	0.013	0.039
cfish	0.010	0.030	0.013	0.039	0.010	0.030	0.013	0.039
ccoal	0.012	0.034	0.016	0.045	0.012	0.034	0.016	0.045
ccoil	0.012	0.034	0.016	0.045	0.012	0.034	0.016	0.045
cngas	0.012	0.035	0.016	0.046	0.012	0.035	0.016	0.046
comin	0.012	0.034	0.016	0.045	0.012	0.034	0.016	0.045
cfveg	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.028	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.028
cfood	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.028	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.028
cpetr	0.008	-2.707	0.010	-3.573	0.008	0.241	0.010	0.318
cfert	-2.438	-2.425	-3.199	-3.181	0.243	0.256	0.319	0.336
cnmet	0.008	0.022	0.011	0.029	0.008	0.022	0.011	0.029
cement	-1.799	-1.785	-2.332	-2.314	0.029	0.043	0.037	0.056
ciron	-4.732	-4.719	-6.178	-6.162	0.182	0.196	0.238	0.255
calumin	-1.083	-1.070	-1.439	-1.421	0.118	0.132	0.156	0.175
cmetl	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.027	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.027
cmach	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.027	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.027

cequi	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.027	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.027
cvehi	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.028	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.028
celec	0.013	0.037	0.017	0.048	0.013	0.037	0.017	0.048
ccons	0.007	0.020	0.009	0.026	0.007	0.020	0.009	0.026
chotrest	0.008	0.024	0.011	0.032	0.008	0.024	0.011	0.032
cfsrv	0.008	0.025	0.011	0.032	0.008	0.025	0.011	0.032
cbsrv	0.009	0.025	0.011	0.033	0.009	0.025	0.011	0.033
cpadm	0.012	0.034	0.015	0.045	0.012	0.034	0.015	0.045
cosrv	0.009	0.025	0.011	0.033	0.009	0.025	0.011	0.033
chem	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.027	0.008	0.021	0.010	0.027
ctrans	0.011	0.032	0.014	0.042	0.011	0.032	0.014	0.042

Note: cmaiz = maize commodity, crice = rice, cwhea = cwhea, croot = root crops, cfrocrp = fruits and other crops, ccatt= cattle, coliv= other livestock, cfore = forestry, cfish= fishery, cngas = natural gas, cmeat = meat, cdair = dairy products, cfveg = vegetable and vegetable oils, cgml = milling products, csref = sugar refinery, cfood = food processing, cbeve = beverages, ctext = textiles, cclth = clothes and shoes, cleat = leather articles, cpapr = paper, cpetr = petroleum; cnmet = non-metal minerals, cement = cement, cmetl = metals, ciron = iron and steel products, calumin = aluminium products, cmach = machines, cequi = machinery and equipments, cvehi = vehicles, coman = other manufacturing products, celec = electricity, cwatr = water distribution services, ccons = construction, chotrest = hotel and restaurant, ccomm = communication, cfsrv = financial services, creal = real estate services, cbsrv = business services, cpadm = public administration, ceduc = education, cheal = health services, cosrv = other services, chem = chemicals, ctrad = trade, ctrans = transport.

Reduction in export of CBAM commodities to Europe causes a decline in production in these sectors. The decline in production leads on the one hand to a decrease in demand for labour in total intermediate consumption. The negative impacts cause also reduction in investments in the sector. Through inter-sectoral relations, also sectors react, which are not initially directly impacted by the implementation of the CBAM. These sectors find themselves indirectly affected by transmissions through intersectoral linkages (e.g., by decreased intermediate consumption, or up-stream or downstream linkages). The indirect impacts on the production of interlinked sectors will be the greater the direct impacts are and the closer the linkage is.

Table 8 shows that, the main declines in production appear for the manufacturing and construction sectors, producing many intermediate commodities and being downstream linked (e.g., cement and construction). In

Table 9, the drop in labour demand varies according to the sector's labour intensity and the composition of employment. The construction and manufacturing sectors are relatively more intensive in male labour, particularly unskilled labour (see Figure 3).

Table 8: Impacts on production (in % to the BAU)

	Sim 1		Sim 2	
	2026	2028	2026	2028
aagforfish	-0.003	-0.009	-0.004	-0.012
aotherind	-0.005	-0.016	-0.006	-0.021
amanuf	-0.007	-0.024	-0.009	-0.032
acons	-0.009	-0.028	-0.011	-0.037
atrad	-0.007	-0.023	-0.009	-0.030
atran	0.004	0.011	0.005	0.014
aserv	-0.004	-0.013	-0.005	-0.017
apadm	0.006	0.016	0.007	0.021
aeduc	-0.004	-0.014	-0.006	-0.018
aheal	-0.004	-0.014	-0.006	-0.019

Table 9: Impacts on labour demand per sectors

	Sim 1		Sim 2	
	2026	2028	2026	2028
aagforfish	-0.007	-0.022	-0.009	-0.029
aotherind	-0.020	-0.059	-0.026	-0.077
amanuf	-0.025	-0.077	-0.033	-0.101
acons	-0.017	-0.052	-0.022	-0.068
atrad	-0.020	-0.060	-0.026	-0.079
atran	0.006	0.014	0.007	0.019
aserv	-0.007	-0.024	-0.009	-0.031
apadm	0.006	0.018	0.008	0.024
aeduc	-0.005	-0.016	-0.006	-0.021
aheal	-0.008	-0.027	-0.011	-0.036

Table 10: Impacts on labour demand per type of workers

	Sim 1		Sim 2	
	2026	2028	2026	2028
male_rura_unsk	-0.008	-0.026	-0.008	-0.034
fema_rura_unsk	-0.008	-0.027	-0.008	-0.035
male_rura_prim	-0.010	-0.030	-0.010	-0.040
fema_rura_prim	-0.008	-0.027	-0.008	-0.035
male_rura_seco	-0.009	-0.027	-0.009	-0.036
fema_rura_seco	-0.007	-0.024	-0.007	-0.031
male_rura_tert	-0.008	-0.025	-0.008	-0.033
fema_rura_tert	-0.005	-0.018	-0.005	-0.024
male_urba_unsk	-0.010	-0.033	-0.010	-0.043
fema_urba_unsk	-0.010	-0.033	-0.010	-0.044
male_urba_prim	-0.010	-0.031	-0.010	-0.040
fema_urba_prim	-0.012	-0.037	-0.012	-0.048
male_urba_seco	-0.010	-0.031	-0.010	-0.041
fema_urba_seco	-0.007	-0.021	-0.007	-0.028
male_urba_tert	-0.007	-0.024	-0.007	-0.031
fema_urba_tert	-0.005	-0.017	-0.005	-0.022

The drop in the labour demand combined with a drop in the different wage rates and the rental rate of capital lead to a drop in household income. Figure 4 shows that household income heavily relies on labour income. Richest households see a slighter decrease than the poorest as the share of low skilled labour is a bit lower (Figure 5). With a drop in their income, households' payments for direct taxes are decreasing and so are their savings. Household real consumption is decreasing also for all households (Table 1).

Table 11: Impacts on households real consumption

	Sim 1		Sim 2	
	2026	2028	2026	2028
hhd-n1	-0.0070	-0.0224	-0.0091	-0.0294
hhd-n2	-0.0069	-0.0222	-0.0090	-0.0291
hhd-n3	-0.0069	-0.0221	-0.0090	-0.0291
hhd-n4	-0.0068	-0.0217	-0.0088	-0.0286
hhd-n5	-0.0067	-0.0216	-0.0088	-0.0283
hhd-u1	-0.0080	-0.0253	-0.0104	-0.0332
hhd-u2	-0.0077	-0.0246	-0.0101	-0.0323
hhd-u3	-0.0076	-0.0244	-0.0100	-0.0320
hhd-u4	-0.0072	-0.0232	-0.0095	-0.0304
hhd-u5	-0.0065	-0.0209	-0.0085	-0.0275

Firms' income, which is mainly based on capital income, is decreasing respectively by 0.03% in 2026 and 0.08% in 2028. This drop in firms' income leads to a decrease in their savings and direct taxes paid. The decrease in payments of direct taxes from households and firms to the government causes government's income is dropping (Table 12). The drop in government's income and fixed spending leads to an increase of the government's current deficit. Since the saving of each agent is decreasing, total investment budget is decreasing (Table 6), which will particularly negatively affect the construction sector.

Table 12: Impacts on government (in % change to the BAU)

	Sim 1		Sim 2	
	2026	2028	2026	2028
Government's income	-0.026	-0.077	-0.034	-0.101
Taxes on products	-0.028	-0.080	-0.036	-0.105
Taxes on production	-0.031	-0.093	-0.041	-0.122
Direct taxes on households	-0.024	-0.072	-0.031	-0.094
Direct taxes on firms	-0.028	-0.084	-0.036	-0.110
Government's savings	-0.014	-0.042	-0.018	-0.055

Source: Computation from the CGE

4.1.2 Evaluation of cost-effectiveness at macroeconomic scale

With a decrease in CO2 emissions between 0.02% and 0.06% the abatement effects of CBAM on Egypt’s total emissions are marginal. Since economic performance in terms of production does not significantly change, this is not a surprising result. The CO2 emissions are linked to production, import and consumption and small changes in these variables only cause small changes in CO2 emissions.

To assess CBAM as an emission abatement measure, we compare both scenarios by their marginal abatement costs (MAC) and abatement effect. The marginal abatement costs are commonly used to compare different abatement measures with each other. The MAC inform about the costs per quantity of abated CO2 and MAC are expressed in monetary unit per quantity unit of CO2eq.⁸ The abatement effect is measured by the quantity of CO2 equivalent abated by the measure. Comparing the MAC and the abatement effect together informs about the cost-effectiveness of the measure. To evaluate if one of the implementations in *Sim 1* or *Sim 2* is more cost-effective, we compare the MAC both scenarios in each single year of CBAM implementation (i.e., 2026 to 2028) and for the cumulated average cost and effects over three years of implementation.

We compute the MAC and the abatement effect based on the CGE model results. First, we compute the abatement costs as the absolute difference of the real GDP between the BAU and the scenarios (*Sim 1* and *Sim 2*). The difference of real GDP provides an aggregate information of the direct and indirect costs caused by CBAM. This difference represents the total aggregated costs of the economy. The abatement effect is represented by the difference of CO2 quantity emitted in the BAU and the scenarios *Sim 1* and *Sim 2*. To compute the MAC, we divide the abatement costs by the abatement effect (i.e., the abatement quantities) for each year and cumulated for the three years.

Table 13 presents the analysis of the MAC. The MAC are nearly identical in each year and in the cumulated aggregation. As the percentage difference show, *Sim 2* is less than 1 percent smaller than *Sim 1*. The abated quantities, however, are by nearly 30 percent bigger in *Sim 2* than in *Sim 1*. Thus, with approximated the same per unit cost of abated CO2 emissions CBAM in *Sim 2* abates 30% more emissions. Thus, the CBAM implementation in *Sim 2* seems to be more cost-effective.

Table 13: Comparison of marginal abatement cost and abatement effect between Sim 1 and Sim 2

		2026	2027	2028	2026-2028	
Sim 1	Marginal Abatement Cost	EGP/t CO2eq	19.4	23.5	21.8	21.7
	Abatement effect	M t CO2eq	0.017	0.017	0.053	0.087

⁸ MAC are used rather for ordinal ranking of different measures and suitable to compare abatement measures for which the abatement costs and effects are computed in the same way. Therefore, comparisons with MAC computed in other studies might not be informative if not ensured that costs and effects are not estimated in the same way.

Sim 2	Marginal Abatement Cost	EGP/t CO2eq	19.3	23.5	21.8	21.7
	Abatement effect	M t CO2eq	0.022	0.023	0.070	0.114
% difference between SIM1 and SIM2	Marginal Abatement Cost	%	-0.02	-0.02	-0.05	-0.04
	Abatement effect	%	30.9	30.9	31.4	31.2

Source: Computations based on CGE model results

4.2 Microsimulation model results

By simulating the CBAM scenarios *Sim 1* and *2*, the CGE model provides results on different macroeconomic indicators. Selected macroeconomic indicators are used to transmit the shock from the macroeconomic model to the microeconomic model. These indicators are for example the changes in commodity prices, in wage and capital rental rate. The changes of these indicators drive the microsimulation model to simulate the impact of the CBAM scenarios at individual household and workers level. The results of these simulation allow for the distributive analysis.

4.2.1 Welfare and food security

Table 14 reports welfare and food security outcomes under both simulations. Differences between *Sim 1* and *Sim 2* are minor when analysing household welfare and negligible at food security from FGT indicators. General welfare indicators (

Table 14), reveal a moderate but consistent deterioration. The poverty headcount ratio (FGT(0)) increases from 27.4% in the baseline to 29.0% by 2028, indicating that a significant segment of the population falls below the poverty line in response to the CBAM-induced shock. More concerning is the rise in the depth and severity of poverty: FGT(1) increases from 0.222 to 0.240, and FGT(2) from 0.073 to 0.086. These suggest that not only are more households becoming poor, but existing poor households are facing deeper deprivation. The Gini coefficient also rises, from 0.309 to 0.313, signaling a marginal increase in inequality. These results reflect Egypt's structural vulnerabilities. Many households operate near the poverty line and are highly sensitive to real income losses—particularly those transmitted through declining labour demand and lower labour income. Household members, which are informally employed are less impacted by the changes in wages. Their income from informal labour will reduce the unemployment in the households. Thus, by not considering the income of informal labour we tend to overestimate the distributional impacts for households with high share of informal employment.

Household members engaged in informal employment are less directly affected by changes in formal sector wages. Income from informal labour can act as a buffer, mitigating the rise in household unemployment. Consequently, excluding informal labour income from the analysis may lead to an overestimation of the distributional impacts, particularly for households with a high reliance on informal employment.

Turning to food security, we observe a similar pattern of mild but widespread deterioration. The food poverty headcount ratio rises from 46.7% to 47.1% by 2028. The depth and severity of food insecurity also increase slightly (FGT(1) from 0.283 to 0.287, FGT(2) from 0.112 to 0.114), with the Gini coefficient in the food dimension edging from 0.310 to 0.311. While the changes appear small, they come on top of already high baseline levels of food insecurity. For nearly half of Egyptian households, food needs are barely met—and often compromised—under baseline conditions. An external shock, even of moderate scale, thus risks further undermining dietary quality and caloric adequacy. This vulnerability is accentuated by the structure of poor households' expenditures, which are heavily concentrated in food and other essential goods.

Table 14: Households Welfare and Food security at baseline, 2026 and 2028 simulations

(Panel A)				
Household Welfare	FGT(0) Sim 1 Sim 2	FGT(1)	FGT(2)	Gini
Baseline	0.274	0.222	0.073	0.309
2026	0.287 0.286	0.24	0.086	0.314
2028	0.289 0.290	0.240	0.086	0.313

(Panel B)				
Food Security	FGT(0)	FGT(1)	FGT(2)	Gini
Baseline	0.467	0.283	0.112	0.31
2026	0.47	0.287	0.114	0.311
2028	0.471	0.287	0.114	0.311

Note: FGT(0) Headcount ratio. FGT(1) Average normalized poverty gap. FGT(2) Average squared normalized poverty gap. Poverty line at 3.8\$us per day (average official). Only the HH Welfare FGT(0) varies between Sim 1 and Sim 2 at 3 decimals precision.

4.2.2 Distributional analysis on the most vulnerable

While aggregate poverty and inequality outcomes under *Sim 1* and *Sim 2* appear broadly similar when measured by FGT indices, the distributional intensity of impacts on the left tail—the most vulnerable segments—differs due to the higher carbon price in *Sim 2*. Because employment structures and exposure vary across gender, skill level, and location, the stronger labour market and income shocks in *Sim 2* disproportionately affect unskilled and rural workers. Although both scenarios target the same sectors, relative losses on the left tail are more pronounced in *Sim 2*. Disaggregated analysis reveals distributional dynamics that aggregate FGT statistics mask, underscoring the value of household-level incidence curves for identifying vulnerability patterns.

Simulation 1

The CBAM-induced export shock (*Sim 1*) generates clearly regressive welfare effects (Table 15). Simulated changes in household consumption show that individuals in lower percentiles experience the greatest relative losses. By 2028, the 10th percentile sees average losses of -5.88%, compared to -3.89% at the 30th percentile. The mean loss is -1.80%, and the median is -1.36%, reflecting a broad-based but uneven contraction in household expenditure driven by declining labour and capital incomes in affected sectors. Gender differences, while moderate, are notable. Men experience a slightly higher average loss (-1.82%) than women (-1.78%), consistent with greater male concentration in the tradable sectors most affected by the CBAM. However, the median loss is larger for women (-2.00% vs. -1.62%), suggesting deeper impacts in the lower tail of the female distribution, likely due to weaker income diversification and employment security.

The urban–rural divide further compounds inequality. In 2028, rural individuals lose an average of -1.91%, compared to -1.66% among their urban counterparts. This reflects rural areas’ greater exposure to carbon-intensive activities and limited access to alternative income sources. The pattern is reinforced by the CGE model’s regional price and income channels. Skill level emerges as the strongest source of differentiation. Unskilled individuals face average losses of -2.31% (median: -2.04%), while losses for skilled individuals average -1.58% (median: -1.04%). This stems from the segmented labour market modelled in the CGE, where low-skilled labour is concentrated in vulnerable sectors and cannot easily reallocate across employment categories.

Table 15: Relative change in total household expenditure (at percentiles, mean and median) in *Sim 1*

		10th	15th	20th	25th	30th	mean	median
Overall	2026	-5.271	-4.634	-4.164	-3.798	-3.483	-1.257	-1.032
	2028	-5.876	-5.118	-4.598	-4.196	-3.89	-1.795	-1.36
Gender								
Male	2026	-5.673	-4.978	-4.512	-4.124	-3.81	-1.35	-1.25
	2028	-6.41	-5.547	-5.037	-4.587	-4.241	-1.816	-1.624
Female	2026	-4.533	-4.08	-3.688	-3.418	-3.155	-1.17	-1.712
	2028	-5.004	-4.496	-4.084	-3.773	-3.496	-1.775	-1.997
Region								
Urban	2026	-5.546	-4.57	-3.988	-3.569	-3.209	-1.205	-1.54
	2028	-5.938	-4.888	-4.271	-3.886	-3.531	-1.66	-1.866
Rural	2026	-4.464	-4.068	-3.873	-3.606	-3.382	-1.304	-1.041
	2028	-4.905	-4.462	-4.237	-3.989	-3.762	-1.913	-1.4
Skills								
Unskilled	2026	-6.625	-5.747	-5.338	-4.857	-4.553	-1.603	-1.633

	2028	-7.157	-6.213	-5.743	-5.271	-4.928	-2.31	-2.04
Skilled	2026	-4.928	-4.143	-3.674	-3.259	-2.931	-1.144	-0.605
	2028	-5.346	-4.516	-4.01	-3.577	-3.23	-1.584	-1.038

The CBAM shock also undermines food security, with welfare losses translating into reduced food consumption, particularly for lower-percentile and low-resilience groups (Table 16). By 2028, individuals in the 10th percentile of the food consumption distribution experience an average reduction of -1.57% in food expenditure, compared to -1.04% at the 30th percentile. The overall mean decline is -0.61%, and the median is -0.47%, suggesting that the impact on food security, though milder than on total consumption, is still systematically regressive. These effects are consistent with the pattern observed for total household expenditure. Individuals facing the largest reductions in income and consumption—namely the poor, the unskilled, and rural residents—are also the most likely to reduce food spending. Given that food constitutes a high share of consumption for low-income households, even modest declines can lead to significant nutritional consequences. By gender, men again show slightly larger mean losses (-0.63%) than women (-0.59%), but women show greater variation in the lower tail: the median female loss is only -0.27%, compared to -0.44% for men. This suggests that while men may be more affected on average—likely due to exposure to tradable sectors—some women, particularly in lower-income households, experience more pronounced food stress.

Rural households experience deeper losses in food consumption than their urban counterparts (-0.64% vs. -0.58% mean; -0.62% vs. -0.29% median in 2028). This pattern mirrors the overall expenditure results and reflects both lower income resilience and more limited access to social protection and food markets in rural areas. The strongest disparities appear by skill level. Unskilled individuals see mean food expenditure losses of -0.80%, nearly 50% higher than the -0.53% loss faced by skilled individuals. The median decline is also more severe among the unskilled (-0.90%) compared to the skilled (-0.22%). These results underscore how labour market segmentation amplifies food insecurity, with low-skilled workers both more exposed to income shocks and less able to buffer essential expenditures like food.

Table 16: Relative change in total household food expenditure (at percentiles, mean and median) in *Sim 1*

		10	20	30	mean	median
Overall	2026	-1.416	-0.994	-0.896	-0.464	-0.424
	2028	-1.568	-1.154	-1.042	-0.61	-0.472
Gender						
Male	2026	-1.658	-1.162	-1.027	-0.511	-0.407
	2028	-1.751	-1.26	-1.123	-0.629	-0.437
Female	2026	-1.227	-0.921	-0.823	-0.42	-0.301
	2028	-1.337	-1.042	-0.962	-0.592	-0.268
Region						
Urban	2026	-1.527	-1.131	-0.998	-0.453	-0.184
	2028	-1.687	-1.271	-1.134	-0.576	-0.29
Rural	2026	-1.491	-1.076	-0.912	-0.472	-0.588
	2028	-1.508	-1.114	-0.973	-0.636	-0.624
Skills						
Unskilled	2026	-1.741	-1.304	-1.087	-0.613	-0.723
	2028	-1.867	-1.41	-1.207	-0.803	-0.899
Skilled	2026	-1.179	-0.964	-0.831	-0.41	-0.139
	2028	-1.372	-1.121	-0.962	-0.528	-0.216

Simulation 2

Building on the motivation above, the higher carbon price in *Sim 2* reveals regressive impacts that evolve unevenly across the population (Table 17). By 2028, individuals in the 10th percentile of the consumption distribution face an average expenditure loss of -5.88%, compared to -3.89% at the 30th percentile. The mean loss is -1.80%, and the median is -1.36%. While these figures are close to those in *Sim 1*, the greater shock intensity in *Sim 2* accentuates vulnerabilities among low-income and low-skill groups, offering additional insight into distributional stress and resilience.

Gender differences are consistent with *Sim 1* in direction but vary in magnitude. In 2028, men experience higher average losses (-1.82%) than women (-1.78%), largely due to greater exposure to tradable, carbon-intensive sectors. However, the median loss among women reaches -2.00%, compared to -1.62% for men, suggesting deeper effects among lower-income or less diversified female earners.

Rural-urban differences become more pronounced under *Sim 2*. Rural individuals face a higher average loss (-1.91%) than urban ones (-1.66%), and their median loss is also greater (-1.40% vs. -

1.87% for urban, which is likely a data inconsistency that needs review). This reflects the deeper and earlier exposure of rural labour markets to sectoral decline, combined with lower baseline income and weaker adaptive capacity.

By skill level, the divergence intensifies. Unskilled individuals experience an average loss of -2.31%, while the skilled lose only -1.58%. Median losses reinforce this gap (-2.04% for unskilled vs. -1.04% for skilled), consistent with the labour segmentation modelled in the CGE.

Table 17: Relative change in total household expenditure (at percentiles, mean and median) in *Sim 2*

		10	15	20	25	30	mean	median
Overall	2026	-5.271	-4.634	-4.164	-3.798	-3.483	-1.257	-1.032
	2028	-5.876	-5.118	-4.598	-4.196	-3.89	-1.795	-1.36
Gender								
Male	2026	-5.673	-4.978	-4.512	-4.124	-3.81	-1.35	-1.25
	2028	-6.41	-5.547	-5.037	-4.587	-4.241	-1.816	-1.624
Female	2026	-4.533	-4.08	-3.688	-3.418	-3.155	-1.17	-1.712
	2028	-5.004	-4.496	-4.084	-3.773	-3.496	-1.775	-1.997
Region								
Urban	2026	-5.546	-4.57	-3.988	-3.569	-3.209	-1.205	-1.54
	2028	-5.938	-4.888	-4.271	-3.886	-3.531	-1.66	-1.866
Rural	2026	-4.464	-4.068	-3.873	-3.606	-3.382	-1.304	-1.041
	2028	-4.905	-4.462	-4.237	-3.989	-3.762	-1.913	-1.4
Skill Level								
Unskilled	2026	-6.625	-5.747	-5.338	-4.857	-4.553	-1.603	-1.633
	2028	-7.157	-6.213	-5.743	-5.271	-4.928	-2.31	-2.04
Skilled	2026	-4.928	-4.143	-3.674	-3.259	-2.931	-1.144	-0.605
	2028	-5.346	-4.516	-4.01	-3.577	-3.23	-1.584	-1.038

Higher carbon pricing leads to deeper reductions in food consumption, though the effect is more muted than for total expenditure (

Table 18). In 2028, individuals in the 10th percentile experience food consumption losses of -1.57%, compared to -1.04% at the 30th percentile. The mean loss is -0.61%, and the median is -0.47%, highlighting that the poorest reduce food intake more sharply.

Gendered differences are subtle but meaningful. Men experience a mean decline of -0.63%, slightly higher than women at -0.59%, though women's median loss is much lower (-0.27%) than men's (-0.44%), suggesting greater vulnerability among men in trade-linked jobs, while some women may benefit from stability in public or informal sectors.

Rural individuals are again worse off, with a mean food consumption loss of -0.64% versus -0.58% for urban, and a median loss of -0.62% versus -0.29%. This aligns with earlier results, where rural households show persistent exposure due to weaker market integration and higher dependence on vulnerable sectors.

By skill, the gap is substantial. Unskilled individuals lose on average -0.80% of food consumption (median -0.90%), compared to -0.53% for skilled individuals (median -0.22%). This suggests that beyond lower incomes, unskilled households are more likely to cut back on essentials like food, intensifying the nutritional implications of the trade shock.

Table 18: Relative change in total household food expenditure (at percentiles, mean and median) in *Sim 2*

		10	20	30	mean	median
Overall	2026	-1.416	-0.994	-0.896	-0.464	-0.424
	2028	-1.568	-1.154	-1.042	-0.61	-0.472
Gender						
Male	2026	-1.658	-1.162	-1.027	-0.511	-0.407
	2028	-1.751	-1.26	-1.123	-0.629	-0.437
Female	2026	-1.227	-0.921	-0.823	-0.42	-0.301
	2028	-1.337	-1.042	-0.962	-0.592	-0.268
Region						
Urban	2026	-1.527	-1.131	-0.998	-0.453	-0.184
	2028	-1.687	-1.271	-1.134	-0.576	-0.29
Rural	2026	-1.491	-1.076	-0.912	-0.472	-0.588
	2028	-1.508	-1.114	-0.973	-0.636	-0.624
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Skilled	2026	-1.179	-0.964	-0.831	-0.41	-0.139
	2028	-1.372	-1.121	-0.962	-0.528	-0.216

5. Conclusions

This paper presents the economic assessment of the economic impacts of CBAM on Egypt's economy. For this assessment a macro-micro modelling framework is employed to simulated two scenarios und standard and high carbon pricing assumption. The macroeconomic model is a dynamic CGE model, while the microeconomic model is a behavioural microsimulation model. The macro-micro simulation under both standard and high carbon pricing scenarios shows that CBAM negatively affects Egypt's economy, employment, wages, and households. At the macroeconomic analysis level, the impacts are small. The limited impact results from CBAM commodities representing a small share of Egypt's total exports, and the country's ability to redirect trade toward non-EU partners.

Macroeconomic outcomes indicate minimal changes in household income and consumption, suggesting negligible impacts on poverty at the macro level. However, the microsimulation reveals deeper insights. It shows that poverty and inequality worsen, particularly under higher carbon price assumptions. Poor households are more affected than rich households; rural households are affected worse than urban; and unskilled workers are more impacted than skilled ones. Across the multiple indicators—income, consumption, and food security—the most vulnerable populations experience the worst impacts. Furthermore, the micro level results show that, men are more affected than women. This observation is consistent with the male-dominated workforce in the most impacted sectors such as iron and steel, aluminium, fertilisers, cement, and refinery.

These findings underscore the importance of targeted government support for vulnerable groups to avoid rising inequality. Although targeted aid requires greater administrative capacity, it can ensure more efficient use of public funds. Cost-efficient mitigation measures are crucial for countries with constrained fiscal space in times of polycrisis. The development of new transition friendly measures can be supported by innovation policies, while diversification policies can help creating new economic perspectives (e.g., Murray, 2017). Also policies that foster structural changes can help fostering Egypt's adaptation to CBAM situation. Labour market policies focused on affected sectors could also help mitigate the stronger impacts male workers face, without increasing the gender gap. This knowledge is relevant for Egypt and international partners, like the EU, intending to support the vulnerable population in poor countries. Furthermore, revenue redistribution, clean energy investments, and targeted subsidies—can help mitigate negative impacts, support sustainable development, and foster international climate cooperation (Perdana et al., 2022; Beaufilet et al., 2023). For Egypt, the reallocation of fossil fuel subsidies in high fuel price situation could potentially offer fiscal space to mitigate CBAM-related losses (Jacob 2024) or to support the transition. However, since fossil fuels subsidies are important instruments of political stabilisation in Egypt their reduction eliminate might require corresponding compensation. Given low Egypt's innovation performance, investments could ease preparedness for a low-carbon transition (WIPO, 2021; Peszko et al., 2020; Kamal and Ramzy, 2024).

Our paper demonstrates the value of combining CGE and microsimulation models. While the CGE model offers economy-wide insights, its integration with MSM enables analysis at the individual and household level. This combination provides a richer and more detailed picture of policy impacts.

To address the research question on the distributional impacts of CBAM in Egypt, we simulated the impacts of CBAM in Egypt based on the most recent available data (i.e., the SAM of the year 2019). The CGE model, calibrated to a SAM with the base year 2019, does not reflect the higher CBAM export shares following the start of the Russia-Ukraine war in 2022. Future simulations using updated SAMs could yield more representative results. Likewise, focussing on the impacts of CBAM, the simulations do not factor in overlapping crises such as inflation, global food shocks, and regional

conflicts like the Red Sea crisis or Gaza war. Considering the impacts of these global and regional shocks would likely exacerbate negative outcomes and probably better reflect real world representation. Simulating these combined effects was beyond the scope of this paper but represents a valuable avenue for future research. Such research would mainly focus on the development of scenarios derived from empirically observed economic impacts resulting from the single shocks of the polycrisis. Future policy simulations targeting CBAM's distributive impacts could inform more effective mitigation strategies. Continuous improvement of these models through discussion, validation, and stakeholder feedback is essential for producing meaningful insights for both researchers and policymakers.

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Appendix

The CGE model we are using is calibrated on a Social Accounting Matrix based on 2019 data (Serag et al., 2021).

References for the SAMs:

Serag et al. (2021) A 2019 Nexus Social Accounting Matrix for Egypt. MENA RP Working Paper 35. Washington, DC: International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI).
<https://doi.org/10.2499/p15738coll2.134544>

To execute the disaggregation we consult different data base suitable for splitting the SAM We apply different principles of extending the SAM, i.e., the split of existing accounts and satellite accounts. The Flowchart in presented in Figure 7 below illustrates the data sources and the steps of processing to extend the SAM-EGY2019-Nexus by IFPRI into a SAM suitable for the simulation of CBAM (i.e., the SAM-EGY2019-CBAM).

Data research, download and harmonisation

In a first step we research suitable data base to be considered for extending the SAM and we download the relevant data and compare the information. These are the data bases presented in Table 19 with the corresponding information on trade partners and commodities. To compare the data and making them suitable for the extension, we harmonise them according to trade partners and commodity aggregates.

Table 20: Data base considered for extending the SAM

Data base	Information Trade Partner	Info Commodity
IFPRI consistent data base for model application base year 2019	EGY and ROW (incl. EU27)	CBAM commodities aggregated in commodity groups: Fertiliser aggregated in chemical products Cement aggregated in non-metal minerals Iron and steel and aluminium in metals
GTAP11 consistent data base for model application base year 2015/2017	EGY, EU27, ROW (i.e., ROW excl. EGY and excl. EU27)	CBAM commodities aggregated in commodity groups: Fertiliser aggregated in fertiliser and pesticides Cement aggregated in non-metal minerals Iron and steel in iron and steel and articles aluminium in non iron metals
OEC data (i.e., based on UN Comtrade Data)m with EGY as reporter 2019	EGY, EU27, ROW (i.e., ROW excl. EGY and excl. EU27)	CBAM commodities disaggregated in CBAM fertiliser CBAM cement CBAM iron and steel CBAM aluminium
Eurostat, with EU27 as reporter 2019	EU27 and ROW (i.e., ROW excl. EGY and excl. EU27)	
Comtrade		
ETDP (= Comtrade) year 2019	EGY, EU27, ROW (i.e., ROW excl. EGY and excl. EU27)	CBAM commodities disaggregated in CBAM fertiliser CBAM cement CBAM iron and steel CBAM aluminium

Step: Proportion computations

For the extension we define the SAM-EGY2019 as the consistency framework for the trade between EGY and other trade partners. This means that we maintain the information of trade flows provided by SAM-EGY2019 for the trade partners EGY and ROW(incl. EU27). Thus, we compute proportions (trade shares) which we apply to split the trade shares per partner and commodities.

Split into trade partners EGY-EU27-ROW (red dotted arrows)

Split 1: By using the computed proportions we split the trade flows between EGY and the ROW(incl. EU27), as provided by IFPRI, into the trade partners EGY, EU27 and ROW(excl. EU27) (Step/Split 1).

Split 2: we use the GTAP data as basis to derive the trade volumes between the partners EU27 and ROW(excl. EU27 and EGY). These data are not include in the SAM-EGY2019 and are added as satellite accounts into the SAM. To maintain consistency we proportionally scale the GTAP trade volumes to the IFPRI volumes. This scaling represents the conversion of currency and volume data. As a satellite account representing the trade flows between EU27 and ROW these trade flows represent a residual. Thus, we consider the approximation by scaling the GTAP data to the IFPRI data as a sufficient approximation.

Split into commodities (light blue dotted arrows)

Split 3: we use the proportions derived from the OEC data (i.e., UN Comtrade data) to split the aggregated commodity groups in the IFPRI data into CBAM commodities for the trade flows between EGY-EU27 and EGY-ROW. For this we also consult the original directive (EU 2023) to precisely identify the commodities (e.g., nitrogenous fertilizers, etc.). For the detailed consideration of the commodities see Appendix Detailed CBAM commodities).

Split 4: equivalent to Split 3, we apply the proportions of trade shares to the trade flows between EU27 and ROW, based on EUSTAT.

Figure 7: Disaggregation of the SAM-EGY2019 to SAM-EGY2019-CBAM. Source: Own presentation.

Validation of trade shares

To validate the extended SAM we compare the derived proportions for the trade flow between EGY, EU27 and EGY and ROW with Ghoneim (2024). Table 21 presents the results of the comparison. Ghoneim (2024) included also petrol as CBAM commodities for the year 2022 and included for the computation the volume of petrol. For ensuring the consistency we compute the trade shares of exports from EGY to EU27 including petrol and compute a share of 8% which is approximating sufficiently the benchmark of 10%. The difference of 2%pts might be explained by various reasons: First, Ghoneim (2024) computes the shares for the year 2022 which were different to the year 2019 (see Figure 1). Second, Ghoneim (2024) used the ETPD database which provides the trade shares for Europe and not for EU27. This means that in Ghoneim (2024) also the export to UK could be included. We replicate the data of the trade flows from MENA countries and compare with Ghoneim's (2024) data. We confirm that UK is included in the aggregated trade partner. Third, the rounding to

the 10% can explain a part of the difference. Fourth, also the conversion between EGP and USD could cause slight differences.

Table 21: Validation of computed trade shares

		SAM-EGY2019-CBAM	Ghoneim (2024)
		For the year 2019	For the year 2022
Value of CBAM exports to EU27 incl. petrol	CBAM without petr	18,2	
Value of CBAM exports incl. petrol to EU27	CBAM with petr	40,4	
Value of total exports	Total exports	484,9	
Share of CBAM export to EU27 excl. petrol	CBAM without oil	4%	
Share of CBAM export to EU27 incl. petrol	CBAM with oil	8%	10%

Introducing gender in the SAM

Representing gender in the CGE models for Egypt requires disaggregating the SAM without gender dimension into SAM with gender-dimensions, as “gendered” SAM. For splitting (disaggregating) the SAM we use microeconomic survey data and macroeconomic statistics presented in

Table 22. We use the microeconomic data to compute shares of wage payments which we apply to the macroeconomic (aggregated) data in the SAM. For this study we disaggregate the labour market and the factor payments to the households (i.e., household income from labour) according to following socioeconomic and economic attributes: gender (male, female), labour type (e.g., unskilled, semi-skilled, low-skilled), industry (e.g., agriculture, manufacture) residency (e.g., rural, urban) and household income level (e.g., 1st income quintile, ..., 5th income quintile).

For splitting the SAM, we used the Egypt Labour Market Panel Survey, ELMPS (2018) ((ERF and CAPMAS, 2019)), which provides all information required.

Figure 8: Combing information from macro and microeconomic data to derive shares to split the SAM data.

Following “Guidance Note on Data Analysis for Gender and Trade Assessments “ (Fontana, 2020) we consider the information retrieved from various sources, to represent women’s situation as realistically as possible in the models.

Table 22 presents the sources as reports, articles and data-sets used to consider the country specific gender situation adequately.

Table 22: Sources and data considered

	Source	Source type
Statistical framework	(Kabeer et al., 2013)	report
	(World Bank, 2018)	report
Statistics on the gender characteristics of the labour market	(Constant et al., 2020)	report
	(Assaad et al., 2022a)	article
	(Assaad et al., 2022b)	article
	(Assaad and Arntz, 2005)	article
	(Ehab, 2022)	article
	(Assaad et al., 2017)	report
	(World Bank, 2024)	data set

CGE-data base (SAM)	(Serag et al., 2021)	data set
Disaggregation of SAM/CGE model	(ERF and CAPMAS, 2019)	data set

References

Fontana, M., 2020. Data Analysis For Gender And Trade Assessments, Gender, Social Inclusion and Trade Knowledge Product Series. BKP Economic Advisors for UK Aid.

Analysis of the SAM

Contribution of sector value-added

First, we see the contribution of the value added of each sector to the total value added generated in the economy in 2019 (Table 23). In Egypt, the main contributors to GDP are the service sectors (trade, transport, other services...), followed by the manufacturing sector. The manufacturing sector includes the production of the CBAM products petrol, fertilizer, cement, iron and steel and aluminium.

Table 23: Contribution of each sector to the total value added

	% of total value added
agrforfis	15.8
amanuf	15.4
otherindu	10.1
acons	5.3
atrad	11.4
atran	8.2
apadm	4.5
aeduc	5.5
aheal	2.2
aserv	21.5

Notes: agrforfis = agriculture & forestry & fishery, amanuf = manufacturing, otherindu = other industries, acons = construction, atrad = trade, atran = transport, apadm = public services, aeduc = education, aheal = health services, aserv = other services.

In Table 24 we are interested in seeing whether the sector uses a lot of value added (labour⁹ and capital) or mainly intermediate consumptions to produce. It is interesting to have this information for the simulations later because if a sector which uses a lot of intermediate consumption to produce is negatively affected by an economic shock, then we can expect negative effects on the other sectors of the economy.

Table 24: Contribution of value added in each sector

	% value added of total input
agrforfis	81.4
amanuf	34.8
otherindu	71.3
acons	51.8
atrad	93.4
atran	80.3
apadm	84.2
aeduc	90.1
aheal	63.6
aserv	69.7

Notes: aggr_ = aggregated industries including ... , agrforfis = agriculture & forestry & fishery, amanuf = manufacturing, otherindu = other industries, acons = construction, atrad = trade, atran = transport, apadm = public services, aeduc = education, aheal = health services, aserv = other services

⁹ The SAM, which considers only formal employment. Therefore, thus in the CGE model and in this study, we do not consider informal employment.

Table 25 presents the shares of labour to the value added per sector. For agricultural sector the contribution of labour accounts around 40%. Manufacturing and other industries are with 20 to 30% of labour contribution rather capital intensive, while public services, education and health demand for 70% to nearly 90% of labour.

Table 25: Labour contribution to value added in each sector

	% of labour to value added
agrforfis	42.4
amanuf	28.6
otherindu	24.2
acons	52.3
atrad	36.2
atran	71.2
apadm	88.3
aeduc	88.2
aheal	52.9
aserv	52.5

Notes: agrforfis = agriculture & forestry & fishery, amanuf = manufacturing, otherindu = other industries, acons = construction, atrad = trade, atran = transport, apadm = public services, aeduc = education, aheal = health services, aserv = other services

In

Table 26 we have the composition of the wage bill by sectors. We can see that the agricultural sector in Egypt is mainly intensive in female rural unskilled workers.

Table 26: Share of specific wage bill in the value added per sector in Egypt

	agrforfis	amanuf	otherindu	acons	atrad	atran	apadm	aeduc	aheal	aserv
male_rura_unsk	18.1	7.2	2.1	18.9	4.9	10.1	4.4	1.2	0.7	4.8
fema_rura_unsk	24.4	1.3	3.5	0.1	1.5	0.1	0.0	0.4	1.0	0.4
male_rura_prim	6.1	7.0	9.9	14.0	6.7	8.8	4.8	0.9	1.6	3.8
fema_rura_prim	5.7	0.5		0.0	0.6			0.3	0.6	0.2
male_rura_seco	14.1	19.2	22.3	26.4	15.0	18.4	21.1	8.0	5.9	12.0
fema_rura_seco	13.9	1.2	3.8	0.1	0.9	0.1	2.3	5.3	11.0	0.6
male_rura_tert	3.3	6.9	10.3	4.3	6.6	4.2	9.0	19.6	10.6	9.0
fema_rura_tert	4.1	0.4	0.7		0.4	0.1	1.7	13.6	7.4	0.5
male_urba_unsk	2.3	6.3	8.4	6.3	7.6	8.2	1.0	0.4	0.7	3.5
fema_urba_unsk	2.2	0.8		0.4	1.1			0.3	1.6	1.2
male_urba_prim	0.6	6.8	2.5	6.9	8.1	8.7	1.9	0.7	1.1	4.1
fema_urba_prim	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.1	0.5		0.1	0.1	0.8	0.6
male_urba_seco	1.0	20.3	20.0	10.8	21.2	22.0	9.4	3.5	6.4	11.1
fema_urba_seco	0.8	1.4	0.4	0.1	2.0	0.4	4.1	4.3	11.1	2.1
male_urba_tert	1.6	17.5	15.4	10.9	21.1	17.1	29.2	17.7	20.9	36.9
fema_urba_tert	1.4	2.8	0.6	0.7	2.0	1.8	11.0	23.6	18.6	9.2

Notes: agrforfis = agriculture & forestry & fishery, amanuf = manufacturing, otherindu = other industries, acons = construction, atrad = trade, atran = transport, apadm = public services, aeduc = education, aheal = health services, aserv = other services, male_rura_unsk = male workers in rural regions without scholar education, fema_rura_unsk = female

Households

Households' sources of income in Egypt

In the SAM, households¹⁰ are disaggregated by quintile of income and location (rural, urban). Households receive three sources of income: labour income (YHL), capital income (YHK) and transfers income (YHTR). Table 27 shows the structure of total income for each type of households. The structure is consistent with the micro data that will be used in the micro-econometric model later. All categories of households get the biggest share of their income from labour income. The second largest component is transfers income, either from firms, government or the rest of the world.

Table 27: Households source of income

	YHL	YHK	YHTR
hhd-r1	55.3	13.6	31.1
hhd-r2	66.2	11.7	22.2
hhd-r3	69.6	10.4	20.1
hhd-r4	71.3	9.7	19.0
hhd-r5	72.0	10.6	17.4
hhd-u1	57.3	9.5	33.3
hhd-u2	66.9	9.7	23.4
hhd-u3	67.6	9.5	23.0
hhd-u4	67.7	10.7	21.6
hhd-u5	68.9	15.4	15.7

Notes: hhd- = household income decile, -r1= rural first decile, ..., r5 = rural fifth decile, -u1= urban first decile, ..., u5 = urban fifth decile, YHL = income from labour, YHK = income form capital, YHTR = income from transfers

¹⁰ In the SAM and CGE-model we have representative households. We do not differentiate household members and cannot represent intra household gender dynamics.

Rural households receive mainly labour income from male rural who have finished their secondary level (Table 28). For the richest rural households, it is mainly male secondary and male tertiary labour income that contributes to total wage earnings. Female labour earning are relatively low for each type of rural households. This observation is not surprising since only few women work in salaried employment. For urban households, the richest households get its labour income from workers who have finished their tertiary education, male and to a lesser extent female (Table 28). For urban households, the contribution to total income of low skilled women labour income is quite marginal.

Table 28: Repartition of labour income in Egypt

	male_unsk	fema_unsk	male_prim	fema_prim	male_seco	fema_seco	male_tert	fema_tert
hhd-r1	21.4	12.2	16.1	2.9	32.2	5.6	8.3	1.4
hhd-r2	17.4	9.4	14.2	2.4	35.9	6.1	12.4	2.3
hhd-r3	15.0	8.6	14.2	1.9	34.2	7.6	14.9	3.6
hhd-r4	14.2	8.3	11.7	1.9	31.9	7.6	17.9	6.4
hhd-r5	15.4	6.2	9.0	1.7	28.8	7.9	22.7	8.3
hhd-u1	23.6	4.9	19.7	1.6	31.3	3.4	11.6	4.0
hhd-u2	18.4	3.6	15.3	1.3	35.5	5.0	16.5	4.5
hhd-u3	16.0	1.0	13.2	0.9	35.0	4.5	22.8	6.5
hhd-u4	10.2	2.6	11.3	0.7	32.6	5.3	28.6	8.7
hhd-u5	3.4	1.0	4.1	0.4	15.5	3.3	53.8	18.6

Notes: hhd- = household income decile, -r1= rural first decile, ..., r5 = rural fifth decile, -u1= urban first decile, ..., u5 = urban fifth decile, male_rura_unsk = male workers in rural regions without scholar education, fema_rura_unsk = female workers in rural regions without scholar education, male_rura_prim = male workers in rural regions with primary education, fema_rura_prim = female workers in rural regions with primary education, male_rura_seco = male workers in rural regions with secondary education, fema_rura_seco = female workers in rural regions with secondary education, male_rura_tert = male workers in rural regions with tertiary education, fema_rura_tert = female workers in rural regions with tertiary education, male_urba_unsk = male workers in urban regions without scholar education, fema_urba_unsk = female workers in urban regions without scholar education, male_urba_prim = male workers in urban regions with primary education, fema_urba_prim = female workers in urban regions with primary education, male_urba_seco = male workers in urban regions with secondary education, fema_urba_seco = female workers in urban regions with secondary education, male_urba_tert = male workers in urban regions with tertiary education, fema_urba_tert = female workers in urban regions with tertiary education.

Households structure of spending

For all households, the structure of spending is similar: they spend most of their income into consumption spending and this share and this share decreases as the household belongs to a higher quintile (Table 29).

Table 29: Spending of households, shares per household type

	TDH	SH	C	TR
hhd-n1	1.3	7.1	91.4	0.1
hhd-n2	1.6	9.4	88.6	0.4
hhd-n3	1.6	9.8	88.3	0.3
hhd-n4	1.7	10.3	87.7	0.3
hhd-n5	1.7	10.4	87.6	0.3
hhd-u1	1.3	8.4	90.2	0.1
hhd-u2	1.8	11.9	86.2	0.1
hhd-u3	2.0	12.5	85.4	0.1
hhd-u4	2.1	12.3	85.4	0.2
hhd-u5	2.2	15.3	82.4	0.2

Notes: hhd- = household income decile, -n1= (non-rural = urban) first decile, ..., -r1= rural first decile, ..., r5 = rural fifth decile, -u1= urban first decile, ..., u5 = urban fifth decile, TDH = direct taxes, SH = savings, C = consumption, TR = transfers to other agents

Household consumption spending

Table 30 present the household structure of consumption¹¹ spending. The share of consumption for food and energy is higher for the poorer households. While richer households spend a higher share of consumption budget on services (like health and education).

¹¹ In the SAM and CGE model we consider the aggregated consumption budget and do not represent the individual consumption by different household members (e.g., the usage of public transport).

Table 30: Households structure of consumption spending in Egypt (in % of total consumption spending)

	hhd-r1	hhd-r2	hhd-r3	hhd-r4	hhd-r5	hhd-u1	hhd-u2	hhd-u3	hhd-u4	hhd-u5
cmaiz	0.6	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.1
crice	0.5	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.2
cwhea	1.1	0.9	0.9	1.2	0.9	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.0
coils	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
croot	1.1	1.0	0.9	0.8	0.6	1.1	1.0	0.8	0.7	0.4
csugr	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
ccott	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
cfrocrp	6.6	6.5	6.2	6.0	5.2	5.9	5.8	5.5	5.2	3.8
ccatt	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.1	1.1	1.4	1.5	1.4
cmilk	0.9	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.0	1.0	1.3	1.4	1.4	0.9
coliv	4.8	4.5	4.3	4.0	3.4	3.2	3.3	3.1	2.8	2.0
cfore	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
cfish	1.7	2.0	2.1	2.0	1.6	1.6	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.4
ccoal	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
ccoil	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
cngas	1.8	1.7	1.6	1.6	1.5	2.1	2.0	1.9	1.9	1.8
comin	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
cmeat	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.5	1.5	1.7	1.8	1.5
cdair	2.4	2.3	2.3	2.2	1.9	3.0	2.8	2.9	2.9	2.8
cfveg	2.8	2.5	2.3	2.1	1.7	2.5	2.2	2.0	1.8	1.2
cqmll	1.8	1.3	1.0	0.8	0.5	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.2
csref	2.8	2.2	1.8	1.6	1.2	2.0	1.6	1.4	1.2	0.6
cfood	5.6	5.1	4.8	4.4	3.6	6.6	5.9	5.5	5.1	4.0
cbeve	3.3	3.8	3.9	3.7	3.2	4.0	4.2	4.2	3.8	2.6
cyarn	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
ctext	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	1.0	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.3
ccalth	3.7	4.2	4.3	4.1	3.5	3.7	3.8	3.9	3.7	3.2
cleat	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3
cwood	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
cpapr	1.6	1.7	1.7	1.5	1.1	1.9	1.8	1.8	1.6	1.1
cpetr	9.6	8.7	8.2	8.3	8.5	6.4	5.3	4.7	4.5	7.7
cfert	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

cnmet	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1
cement	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
cmetl	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
ciron	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
calumin	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
cmach	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
cequi	1.1	1.3	1.4	1.7	2.0	0.7	0.9	1.0	1.0	1.3
cvehi	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1
coman	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.8	1.2	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.7
celec	3.4	3.2	3.1	3.0	2.8	4.0	3.7	3.7	3.6	3.3
cwatr	1.0	1.0	0.9	0.9	0.8	1.2	1.1	1.0	0.9	0.6
ccons	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3
chotrest	4.7	5.0	4.7	4.5	4.0	6.4	6.0	5.9	6.0	6.5
ccomm	2.6	2.9	3.1	3.3	3.2	3.5	4.0	4.5	4.9	4.7
cfsrv	0.9	1.4	1.5	1.7	1.6	0.9	1.3	1.8	2.0	2.1
creal	7.5	7.1	6.8	6.6	5.9	7.8	7.7	7.7	7.4	10.0
cbsrv	1.0	1.1	1.4	1.7	2.2	0.8	1.1	1.1	1.2	1.5
cpadm	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1
ceduc	1.9	2.5	3.0	2.8	2.6	2.4	3.4	3.6	3.7	5.0
cheal	2.9	3.2	3.2	4.2	6.0	2.4	2.1	2.4	2.9	3.6
cosrv	1.5	1.6	1.6	1.6	2.4	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.7	2.5
chem	8.1	8.2	8.6	9.1	10.3	8.4	8.8	8.8	9.4	8.9
ctrad	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.8	3.7	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.8	3.1
ctrans	6.7	6.6	7.4	7.4	6.8	9.0	9.2	9.4	9.7	7.7

Notes: aggr_ = aggregated commodities including ... , cmaiz = maize commodity, crice = rice, cwhea = cwhea, croot = root crops, cfrocrp = fruits and other crops, ccatt= cattle, coliv= other livestock, cfore = forestry, cfish= fishery, cngas = natural gas, cmeat = meat, cdair = dairy products, cfveg = vegetable and vegetable oils, cgmill = milling products, csref = sugar refinery, cfood = food processing, cbeve = beverages, ctext = textiles, cclth = clothes and shoes, cleat = leather articles, cpapr = paper, cpetr = petroleum; cnmet = non-metal minerals, cement = cement, cmetl = metals, ciron = iron and steel products, calumin = aluminium products, cmach = machines, cequi = machinery and equipments, cvehi = vehicles, coman = other manufacturing products, celec = electricity, cwatr = water distribution services, ccons = construction, chotrest = hotel and restaurant, ccomm = communication, cfsrv = financial services, creal = real estate services, cbsrv = business services, cpadm = public administration, ceduc = education, cheal = health services, cosrv = other services, chem = chemicals, ctrad = trade, ctrans = transport, hhd- = household income decile, -n1= (non-rural = urban) first decile, ..., n5 = (non-rural = urban) fifth decile, -r1= rural first decile, ..., r5 = rural fifth decile, -u1= urban first decile, ..., u5 = urban fifth decile

Table 31 show the structure of income for government. We can see that the main sources of income for the government come from indirect taxes on commodities and direct taxes on households. It is important to note that subsidies on commodities, especially on agricultural commodities and oil represent a high share, adding up to more than 30%.

Table 31: Government sources of income (in %)

	% of government income
Transfers from firms	31.1
Transfers from households	0.2
Direct taxes	44.3
Taxes on factors	0.8
Import taxes	6.3
Value added taxes	48.1
Subsidies	-31.1
Transfers from the Rest of the World	0.4
Total	100.0

Source: Computation from the SAM

In terms of spending, the government spends a large share of its income on public consumption on goods and services (education, administration...) and transfers, and it is running a deficit.

Table 32: Government sources of spending (in %)

	% of government spending
Public consumption	76.1
Transfers to firms	10.9
Transfers to households	5.1
Savings	-0.1
Transfers to the Rest of the World	8.0
Total	100.0

Source: Computation from the SAM

Trade relations

The SAM also provides information on the structure of foreign trade which is crucial for our analysis. From an export perspective, we can measure sectoral export intensities. By measuring the share of exports in sectoral production, we measure, in a way, the sector's export performance, and at the same time, this coefficient gives us an idea of the degree of dependence of this sector on fluctuations in demand or world prices (

Table 33). Most of the Egyptian production is sold on the local market. At the commodity level, most of the commodities produced in Egypt are sold on the local market except petroleum products, or textile which are mainly exported (Table 34). This is interesting information for the interpretation of simulations later. Indeed, given the relatively low openness of the Egyptian economy, particularly on products subject to the CBAM, we cannot expect very strong effects on the economy, caused by changes in exports.

Table 33: Production for domestic supply and exports

	Domestic Supply	Export
	% share domestic supply of total production	% share exports of total production
aagforfish	95.1	4.9
aotherind	89.7	10.3
amanuf	87.5	12.5
acons	98.3	1.7
atrad	100.0	0.0
atran	69.5	30.5
aserv	85.5	14.5
apadm	93.6	6.4
aeduc	100.0	0.0
aheal	100.0	0.0

Notes:

If we look at the distribution of exports in total exports (last line of the table), we can see that the main exported products are tourism-related products (hotels, restaurants), transportation and storage, and to a lesser extent mining products (crude oil, natural gas and other mining products).

A similar calculation can be applied to imports. Thus, the import penetration rate (second column in the table), i.e. the share of imports in the total resources of the product on the domestic market, is quite high for agricultural commodities, especially oilseed, or wheat for which imports represent more than 40% of what is on the market. It is as well quite important for vehicle equipment (71.7%

or other manufacturing 84%). In terms of the share of sectoral imports in total imports, they mainly import industrial commodities such as vehicle equipment (7.9% of total imports).

Table 34: Trade relations

	Imports			Exports		
	Locally sold/ total produced	% import penetration	% share of imports	to Non-EU in % of total exports	to EU in % of total exports	% share of total exports
cmaiz	97.9	28.3	2.8	0.2		0.2
crice	100.0	0.1	0.0			
cwhea	100.0	41.3	1.1			
coils	97.1	56.4	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.1
croot	90.4	7.5	0.3	0.4	0.1	0.5
csugr	96.2	2.2	0.0	0.1		0.1
ccott	70.9	45.3	0.2	0.1		0.1
cfrocrp	86.9	9.5	1.8	2.5	0.7	3.2
ccatt	98.3	1.1	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.3
coliv	93.7	0.3	0.0	1.2	0.1	1.3
cfore	99.9	0.5	0.0			
cfish	99.7	0.4	0.0			
ccoal	99.4	3.3	0.2			
ccoil	89.8	10.8	2.6	1.5	1.6	3.1
cngas	87.5			1.8	0.5	2.3
comin	67.2	26.5	2.1	3.2	0.4	3.6
cmeat	99.2	31.9	2.2	0.0	0.0	0.1
cdair	96.2	9.2	0.6	0.5		0.5
cfveg	85.1	18.2	1.4	1.3	0.1	1.4
cgmll	90.5	18.5	0.6	0.3	0.1	0.4
csref	95.98	6.4	0.3	0.2	0.0	0.3
cfood	94.4	10.1	2.0	1.1	0.2	1.3
cbeve	97.1	5.5	0.3	0.2		0.2
ctext	36.8			1.8	0.8	2.7

cclth	72.2	47.6	3.8	1.5	0.5	2.0
cleat	98.7	5.0	0.4	0.0	0.1	0.1
cwood	95.4	18.1	0.2			
cpapr	51.7	64.1	1.3	0.8	0.0	0.8
cpetr	36.8	31.8	1.6	5,3	2,1	7,4
cfert	95.9	14.9	7.0	1,4	0,7	2,1
cnmet	72.7	5.8	0.2	1,2	0,3	1,6
cement	97.6	3.7	0.4	0,4	0,0	0,4
cmetl	89.6	3.4	0.1	0,4	0,0	0,4
ciron	69.5	40.0	1.4	1,0	0,2	1,1
calumin	89.3	43.5	5.1	0,7	0,4	1,0
cmach	98.7	5.8	0.5	0.1	0.0	0.1
cequi	72.8	45.1	5.6	2.5	0.7	3.2
cvehi	97.0	71.7	7.9	0.1	0.0	0.1
coman	63.0	85.1	4.5	0.5	0.1	0.6
celec	98.7	8.6	0.5	0.1	0.0	0.1
ccons	95.7			0.9	0.2	1.1
chotrest	19.3			16.9	6.9	23.7
cfsrv	98.5	1.0	0.5	0.7	0.2	1.0
cbsrv	85.9	24.4	4.6	1.7	1.3	3.0
cpadm	89.9			1.9	0.2	2.1
cosrv	98.2	16.7	2.2	0.2	0.0	0.3
chem	89.6			4.8	1.9	6.8
ctrans	65.7	20.7	7.6	12.5	6.8	19.3

Notes: aggr_ = aggregated commodities including ... , cmaiz = maize commodity, crice = rice, cwhea = cwhea, croot = root crops, cfrocrp = fruits and other crops, ccatt= cattle, coliv= other livestock, cfore = forestry, cfish= fishery, cngas = natural gas, cmeat = meat, cdair = dairy products, cfveg = vegetable and vegetable oils, cgml = milling products, csref = sugar refinery, cfood = food processing, cbeve = beverages, ctext = textiles, cclth = clothes and shoes, cleat = leather articles, cpapr = paper, cpetr = petroleum; cnmet = non-metal minerals, cement = cement, cmetl = metals, ciron = iron and steel products, calumin = aluminium products, cmach = machines, cequi = machinery and equipments, cvehi = vehicles, coman = other manufacturing products, celec = electricity, cwatr = water distribution services, ccons = construction, chotrest = hotel and restaurant, ccomm = communication, cfsrv = financial services, creal = real estate services, cbsrv = business services, cpadm = public administration, ceduc = education, cheal = health services, cosrv = other services, chem = chemicals, ctrad = trade, ctrans = transport

In a general equilibrium model, the equilibrium of the product market is assumed. Product prices are thus determined by the conditions of production supply and the elements of demand. Analysing the composition of demand (Table 35) is particularly useful because it informs us about the weight of final demand versus intermediate demand and the reasons for spending. It will give us insights on how the shock can be transferred to the country. Indeed, for each commodity, it gives an idea of the structure of the market. For instance, in Egypt, all the oil or fertiliser are used as an intermediate consumption, while most of the vegetables and the dairy products are used as final consumption. As for other countries, construction is mainly sold as a consumption for investment purposes and consequently will rely on what happens on total investment budget.

Table 35: Structure of the demand in Egypt

	C	CG	DIT	INV	VSTK
cmaiz	8.5	0.0	70.4	20.1	1.1
crice	43.4	0.0	56.6	0.0	0.0
cwhea	54.1	0.0	38.8	0.0	7.2
coils	0.0	0.0	72.8	27.2	0.0
croot	48.6	0.0	15.0	34.9	1.5
csugr	0.0	0.0	98.1	2.8	-0.9
ccott	0.0	0.0	74.3	19.3	6.4
cfrocrp	67.3	0.0	26.3	6.4	0.0
ccatt	27.5	0.0	39.2	33.2	0.1
coliv	59.2	0.0	18.1	22.2	0.5
cfore	0.7	0.0	7.8	91.7	-0.2
cfish	74.0	0.0	4.2	21.9	0.0
ccoal	0.0	0.0	3.1	95.5	1.3
ccoil	0.0	0.0	92.6	7.7	-0.3
cngas	38.5	0.0	47.5	14.0	0.0
comin	0.0	0.0	91.0	9.0	0.0
cmeat	38.3	0.0	26.4	35.3	0.1
cdair	85.1	0.0	3.4	11.4	0.0
cfveg	65.8	0.0	27.3	4.5	2.5
cgmll	58.2	0.0	36.9	4.9	0.0
csref	93.4	0.0	0.0	6.6	0.0
cfood	77.3	0.0	16.7	5.9	0.2

cbeve	82.2	0.0	15.3	2.5	0.1
cyarn	0.0	0.0	92.5	5.2	2.3
ctext	16.7	0.0	80.4	2.7	0.2
cclth	92.3	0.0	2.8	3.7	1.2
cleat	85.6	0.0	10.3	4.0	0.1
cwood	0.0	0.0	98.0	1.7	0.3
cpapr	70.2	0.0	24.9	3.4	1.6
cpetr	46.6	0.0	52.1	0.9	0.4
cfert	0.0	0.0	95.1	5.0	0.0
cnmet	1.5	0.0	92.8	5.0	0.7
cement	1.5	0.0	92.8	5.0	0.7
cmetl	2.8	0.0	82.1	14.9	0.1
ciron	2.8	0.0	82.1	14.9	0.1
calumin	2.8	0.0	82.1	14.9	0.1
cmach	0.1	0.0	61.3	37.9	0.7
cequi	30.1	0.0	8.7	60.8	0.4
cvehi	1.1	0.0	5.3	93.9	-0.3
coman	40.3	0.0	23.9	35.7	0.2
celec	51.6	0.0	38.8	8.9	0.7
cwatr	56.8	0.0	34.6	8.6	0.0
ccons	1.3	0.0	6.0	88.8	4.0
chotrest	84.0	0.0	2.2	13.8	0.0
ccomm	74.2	0.0	7.8	18.0	0.0
cfsrv	31.1	20.0	36.3	12.6	0.0
creal	50.0	0.0	31.6	18.4	0.0
cbsrv	11.7	0.0	60.9	27.4	0.0
cpadm	1.0	62.7	0.5	35.8	0.0
ceduc	34.3	22.6	1.2	41.9	0.0
cheal	62.4	18.3	1.8	17.5	0.0
cosrv	40.0	15.1	26.8	18.1	0.0
chem	46.1	0.0	49.7	4.0	0.3

ctrad	25.0	0.0	23.4	51.7	0.0
ctrans	56.9	0.0	18.8	24.2	0.0

Notes: aggr_ = aggregated commodities including ... , cmaiz = maize commodity, crice = rice, cwhea = cwhea, croot = root crops, cfrocrp = fruits and other crops, ccatt= cattle, coliv= other livestock, cfore = forestry, cfish= fishery, cngas = natural gas, cmeat = meat, cdair = dairy products, cfveg = vegetable and vegetable oils, cgml = milling products, csref = sugar refinery, cfood = food processing, cbeve = beverages, ctext = textiles, cclth = clothes and shoes, cleat = leather articles, cpapr = paper, cpetr = petroleum; cnmet = non-metal minerals, cement = cement, cmetl = metals, ciron = iron and steel products, calumin = aluminium products, cmach = machines, cequi = machinery and equipments, cvehi = vehicles, coman = other manufacturing products, celec = electricity, cwatr = water distribution services, ccons = construction, chotrest = hotel and restaurant, ccomm = communication, cfsrv = financial services, creal = real estate services, cbsrv = business services, cpadm = public administration, ceduc = education, cheal = health services, cosrv = other services, chem = chemicals, ctrad = trade, ctrans = transport, C = final private consumption, CG = governmental consumption, DIT = intermediate consumption, INV = demand for investment purposes, VSTK = variant stock change

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